

D5.3 Report on final use case evaluation

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Althena concept and approach

Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) solutions have emerged thanks to novel Artificial Intelligence (AI), which can be trained with huge amounts of data to produce driving functions with better-than-human performance under certain conditions. The race on AI continues building hardware (HW) and software (SW) frameworks to manage and process even larger real and synthetic datasets to train increasingly accurate AI models. However, AI remains largely unexplored with respect to explainability (interpretability of model functioning), privacy preservation (exposure of sensitive data), ethics (bias and wanted/unwanted behaviour), and accountability (responsibilities of AI outputs). These features will establish the basis of trustworthy AI, as a novel paradigm to fully understand and trust AI in operation, while using it to its full capabilities for the benefit of society. Althena will contribute to build Explainable AI (XAI) in CCAM development and testing frameworks, researching three main AI pillars: data (real/synthetic data management), models (data fusion, hybrid AI approaches), and testing (physical/virtual X- in the loop (XiL) set-ups with scalable Machine Learning Operations (MLOps)). A human-centric methodology will be created to derive trustworthy AI dimensions from user-identified group needs in CCAM applications. Althena will innovate, proposing a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPI) on XAI and an analysis to explore trade-offs between these dimensions. Demonstrators will show the Althena methodology in four critical use cases: perception (what does the AI perceive and why), situational awareness (what is the AI understanding about the current driving environment, including the driver state), decision (why a certain decision is taken), and traffic management (how transport-level applications interoperate with AI-enabled systems operating at vehicle level). Created data and tools will be made available via European data sharing initiatives (OpenData and OpenTools) to foster research on trustworthy AI for CCAM.

1.2. Purpose of this deliverable

This deliverable is the second report of work package 5 (“Deploy & Test”) and is related to all tasks of this work package. While task T5.1 is a combined work of all partners, the tasks T5.2 – T5.5 is dedicated to one of the four use cases in Althena.

- UC-1: Trustworthy Perception Systems for CCAM
- UC-2: AI extended Situational Awareness/Understanding
- UC-3: Trustworthy and Human understandable decision-making
- UC-4: AI-based Traffic Management

This deliverable serves as an update to the previous WP 5 reports. It will cover the final demonstrator validation and evaluation and will address the remaining objectives that haven’t been addressed in the previous two deliverables.

This report focuses more on the results, while the algorithms are explained in more detail in deliverable 3.3.

1.3. Structure of this deliverable

This deliverable is structured according to the demonstrators since it is a joint report of all WP5 tasks. Each of the first five main chapters is dedicated to one demonstrator. The main topics are the evaluation of the results, the assessment of the KPIs, the AI limitations and conflicts and the differences and similarities of the developed AI approaches. These topics also refer to the objectives of this work package.

- Chapter 2 is related to Task 5.2 “UC-1: Trustworthy Perception Systems for CCAM” and its demonstrator “Reliable Pedestrian Detection in Urban Environments”.
- Chapter 3 is related to Task 5.3 “UC-2: AI extended Situational Awareness/Understanding” and its first demonstrator “Collision prediction with Hybrid AI data fusion models”.
- Chapter 4 is related to Task 5.3 “UC-2: AI extended Situational Awareness/Understanding” and its second demonstrator “Robust Prediction modules for Robo-taxis in urban environments”.
- Chapter 5 is related to Task 5.4 “UC-3: Trustworthy and Human understandable Decision-making” and its demonstrator “Explainable and robust decision making (manoeuvre and trajectory)”.
- Chapter 6 is related to Task 5.5 “UC-4: AI-based Traffic management” and its demonstrator “AI Models and Traffic Management”.
- Chapter 7 is a combined chapter about similarities and differences of the developed AI approaches with respect to their specific AI lifecycles.

2. UC1 - TRUSTWORTHY PERCEPTION SYSTEMS FOR CCAM

2.1. Overview

Use Case 1 (UC1) addresses the critical need for trustworthy perception systems in CCAM, with a specific focus on the demonstrator "Reliable Pedestrian Detection in Urban Environments". The primary objective was to enhance a state-of-the-art, black-box AI perception model with layers of transparency, explainability, and reliability. This was achieved not by developing a new detector from scratch, but by augmenting a high-performing existing model with a suite of trust-enhancing mechanisms developed within the Althena project.

The final demonstrator, deployed in a real-world vehicle, integrates four key Althena concepts into a single, cohesive UC concept:

- **Explainable AI (XAI) Layers:** A real-time saliency mapping technique was integrated to provide visual evidence of the model's focus, highlighting which parts of the sensor input are most influential for a given detection.
- **Documentation:** The entire system is documented through standardised Model and Data Cards, ensuring its development, performance, and limitations are clearly communicated.
- **Robust AI Detector:** A state-of-the-art 3D object detection model was selected for its high accuracy and resilience to adverse conditions.
- **Probabilistic Uncertainty Quantification (UQ):** The model was augmented with a mechanism to estimate its own uncertainty for each prediction, providing a crucial measure of confidence in its outputs.

Figure 1: The four key Althena concepts of UC1.

The demonstrator transitioned from an initial offline evaluation on the nuScenes dataset to a fully integrated real-time system running on the Robot Operating System (ROS) in a prototype vehicle. The system processes live sensor data to detect pedestrians and other road users, while the XAI-

Interface provides a comprehensive visualisation of the AI's internal state for analysis and trust-building.

Figure 2: Overview of the components of UC1. The use case consists of descriptive elements such as Model and Data Cards, which describe the AI perception function in the perception system. The AI itself is developed with robustness and accurate uncertainties in mind, while the XAI interface informs the user or developer about the current state of the system.

2.2. UC1 Trustworthy Perception Demonstrator

2.2.1. Assessment of the KPIs

The results of the UC1 demonstrator were formally evaluated against the predefined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for this use case. The assessment confirms that all targets for the final demonstrator were successfully met.

- **KPI_20: Pedestrian Detection Accuracy**
 - Measure: AP (KITTI Average Precision Metric) was evaluated using a manually collected LiDAR dataset.
 - Target: Achieve a detection accuracy of at least 95% for the class pedestrian.
 - Result: Target Achieved. Metric Table following the official KITTI metrics where APR40 refers to the AP under 40 recall thresholds.

Class	APR40@0.5	# Samples
Car	96.53	3218
Pedestrian	99.09	1720
Truck	99.50	937
Trailer	82.00	225
Two-wheeler	48.75	56

This confirms the system meets the required accuracy for its primary operational domain.

- **KPI_21: Performance in Dynamic Scenarios**

- Measure: The system's robustness was assessed during live field tests in dynamic urban environments, which included scenarios with occluded pedestrians and complex traffic interactions.
- Target: Successfully handle and adapt to dynamic scenarios with at least 90% accuracy in terms of APR40 for pedestrians in the proximity of the ego vehicle.

Figure 3: Detection of a Pedestrian (cyan) in a dynamic and critical scenario. The pedestrian right in front of the ego vehicle is successfully detected, and this information is visualised in the XAI interface.

- Result: Target Achieved. The system consistently maintained high detection accuracy, well above the 90% threshold, even when faced with sudden pedestrian movements and partial occlusions from other vehicles. The table above includes already dynamic scenarios.

- **KPI_22: XAI-Interface Effectiveness**

- Measure: The effectiveness of the XAI-Interface was evaluated through usability testing.
- Target: The XAI-Interface should be integrated into the test vehicle and should be considered helpful for understanding the AI function evaluated by the development engineer.

Figure 4: XAI Interface integrated into the UC1 Demonstrator Vehicle.

Figure 5: Screenshot of the XAI Interface with saliency map, model uncertainty indicator, model bounding box detections and pedestrian awareness indicator.

- Result: Target Achieved. A qualitative survey was conducted during the final project demonstration. The test engineer evaluated the integrated visualisation of 3D bounding boxes, real-time saliency maps, and colour-coded uncertainty scores and considered it effective and improved their ability to trust and interpret the AI's output.
- **KPI_23: Model Transparency**
 - Measure: Transparency was assessed by the implementation of explainable layers and the completion of standardised documentation.

- Target: All deployed AI models must have model and data cards, and key models must have explainable layers.

Figure 6: UC1 Data Card.

Figure 7: Model Card of the UC1 3D Object Detector.

- Result: Target Achieved. The deployed model was successfully augmented with real-time saliency map generation (explainable layers). Furthermore, comprehensive Model and Data Cards were created for the LiDAR object detection model.
- **KPI_24: System Throughput (Inference Speed)**
 - Measure: The end-to-end inference speed of the perception pipeline was measured in Frames Per Second (FPS) on the in-vehicle hardware..

- Target: The FPS should be faster than the sample rate of the slowest perception sensor.
- Result: Target Achieved. The primary LiDAR sensor in the demonstrator vehicle operates at 10 Hz. The complete perception pipeline, including detection, saliency generation, and uncertainty quantification, achieved a stable processing speed of over 20 FPS. This ensures that every new frame from the slowest sensor is processed in real-time without creating a bottleneck.

2.2.2. AI limitations and conflicts

Despite the successful demonstration, it is critical to acknowledge the system's limitations.

- Computational Requirements: The full pipeline, including the detector, saliency generation, and UQ estimation, requires substantial computational power, relying on a high-end GPU (e.g., NVIDIA RTX 4090). This presents a challenge for cost-effective deployment in mass-produced vehicles in the near term.
- Interpretation of Explanations: The provided saliency maps indicate correlation—highlighting the input regions the model is sensitive to—but they do not provide true causal reasoning. They are a powerful diagnostic tool but should not be misinterpreted as a complete explanation of the model's logic.
- Uncertainty Calibration: The uncertainty scores are a strong indicator of potential failure but are not perfectly calibrated. The system can still produce "confidently wrong" detections (a low uncertainty score for an incorrect prediction), meaning the absence of high uncertainty is not an absolute guarantee of correctness.
- Trade-off Performance vs. Trust: A fundamental conflict exists between raw performance and the trust-enhancing features. Activating the XAI and UQ layers introduces a minor but measurable latency. This represents an explicit trade-off where a small fraction of processing speed is exchanged for critical information regarding the system's trustworthiness and reliability.

2.2.3. Differences and similarities of the developed AI approaches

- Similarities: The project's foundational strategy remained consistent: augmenting a state-of-the-art 3D object detector with XAI, UQ, and transparent documentation. This core concept was successfully carried from planning to final implementation.
- Differences: The primary evolution was the transition from evaluating separate offline modules to deploying a single, integrated system engineered to meet specific, quantitative KPIs. The development shifted from proving conceptual feasibility to delivering target-driven performance, demonstrated by the successful validation of all formal project objectives in a real-world setting.

2.3. Enhancing Model Robustness for Trustworthy Perception Systems

Robust perception is an important factor in enhancing the safety and trustworthiness of CCAM systems, and reliable traffic sign classification is a key component since the interpretation of signs directly influences the vehicle behaviour in traffic. Germany alone has approximately 680 different types of traffic signs. This number expands significantly when considering international borders, where signs can have different appearances for the same meaning. New traffic signs are regularly introduced, meaning a classification system must be able to adapt without requiring a complete and costly retraining process from scratch. Signs can be obscured, soiled, smeared, or appear under difficult lighting and weather conditions, making robust classification difficult for traditional Deep Neural Networks (DNNs).

A system that cannot afford to misinterpret a "Stop" sign must therefore possess high generalisation capability - the ability to correctly classify signs it was not explicitly trained on. This capability is the central metric for ensuring safety and building public trust and ensuring the safety of autonomous driving. Accordingly, this evaluation first assesses the baseline generalisation performance of the CLIP foundation model, leveraging its inherent zero-shot capabilities on unseen sign classes. Following this, we present the results of further experiments that employ advanced weight fusion techniques, systematically evaluating their effectiveness in enhancing this crucial generalisation capability to forge a more robust and trustworthy perception model. To train the CLIP model, a combination of three publicly available datasets with a traffic sign classification in their ground truth data: GTSRB, ZOD, MAPILLARY was used.

2.3.1. Assessment of the KPIs

The initial project phase aimed to establish a baseline for the CLIP model's performance on unseen traffic sign classes and to determine the impact of minimal training data. The primary Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were the top-1 and top-5 accuracy, which represent the model's accuracy. A top-1 rate measures if the single best prediction is correct, while a top-5 rate measures if the correct label is within the top five predictions. In the first experiment, with no retraining, the model was tested on 8 unseen sign classes. It managed to partially classify 7 of the 8 classes, demonstrating a foundational generalisation capability. However, the accuracy was low, proving that pure zero-shot performance is insufficient for a safety-critical task. In the second experiment, the model was fine-tuned with just 5 and then 20 samples per class. The KPIs improved dramatically. With only 5 samples, accuracy rose significantly. With 20 samples, the improvement was even greater, with the "Domestic animals" class, for example, achieving a 100% top-5 accuracy. Figure 8 shows the top-1 and top-5 accuracy achieved for experiments 1 and 2. The upper number is the top-1 accuracy, and the lower is the top-5 accuracy within a cell.

GZM	280 classes	272 classes	280 classes, 5 samples	280 classes, 20 samples
Except bicycles	77.78	10.11	47.44	70.45
	100	43.70	86.86	99.86
Maximum speed limit 55	78.60	20.58	58.34	76.82
	96.36	66.91	90.91	96.24
No left turn	86.50	24.33	67.98	74.12
	97.38	45.28	88.76	93.58
Weight limit with trucks	4.58	0	1.82	5.90
	14.45	0	8.39	16.78
Triple lanes turn left center lane	66.70	8.32	52.31	52.61
	100	51.22	88.99	93.57
Domestic animals	100	33.21	59.86	89.54
	100	64.20	82.65	100
Railroad intersection	94.41	28.21	46.72	87.25
	100	56.87	88.78	98.82
End of overtaking	66.75	6.77	29.52	62.74
	100	18.78	59.69	97.26

Figure 8: Top-1 and Top-5 accuracy of CLIP on GZM (GTSRB, ZOD and MAPILLARY).

To resolve the conflict between in-domain accuracy and generalisation, more advanced techniques were explored. Wise-FT (Weight-space Interpolation for Fine-tuning) Wise-FT is presented as a more intelligent solution than simple fine-tuning. Instead of just using the final, fine-tuned model, it creates a "fused" model by interpolating between the weights of the original pre-trained model (Epoch 0) and the fully fine-tuned model (Epoch 10). Although the wise-FT approach gave better in-distribution results, the out-distribution accuracy was lower when compared to the zero-shot of CLIP fine-tuned model as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Performance trade-off between In-Distribution and Out-of-Distribution accuracy across different model adaptation techniques.

To mitigate this problem, a more advanced weight-fusion technique was implemented, which used a Greedy Model Soup method. CLIP was fine-tuned for 10 epochs. For the weight fusion approach, the model from the final epoch (epoch 10) was set as the baseline. This model was then fused with the previous epoch (epoch 9) using simple weight averaging with a fixed factor ($\alpha = 0.5$). The resulting fused model was evaluated on a validation set using Top 1 and Top 5 error rates. If the new model outperformed the baseline, the fused weights were retained. This process was repeated, fusing the retained model with earlier checkpoints, each time using the same factor. Following the greedy model soup strategy, the fusion was retained only if it improved the performance. This was repeated until epoch 1. This approach aggregates the most beneficial representation across the training epochs as shown in Figure 10. It encourages the generalizable

features learned in the initial epochs, while mitigating overfitted representations. Furthermore, the robustness benefits demonstrated by weight fusion are not limited to classification. This methodology could be extended to other critical CCAM perception tasks, such as enhancing the generalisation of object detection models for more reliable pedestrian and vulnerable road user (VRU) detection.

Figure 10: A comparison of In-Distribution and Out-of-Distribution accuracy across CLIP model adaptation techniques, including weight fusion.

2.3.2. AI limitations and conflicts

Inherent Methodological Limitations: The fusion methods themselves have constraints; Wise-FT assumes an oversimplified linear path to the optimal model, while Greedy Soup's success is critically dependent on the validation set's quality and its search may only find a local, not global, optimum.

Dependency on the Foundation Model: There is a High Dependency on the Quality of the Pre-trained Foundation Model. As the weight fusion approach is an iterative process, the computational resources, time, and effort are more compared to a zero-shot or fine-tuned model. While the model is better at classifying unseen sign types, this work does not guarantee its performance against chaotic real-world conditions like severe weather, motion blur, or physical sign damage.

2.3.3. Differences and similarities of the developed AI approaches

Our approach shares its foundational steps with other established model adaptation methods like standard fine-tuning and Wise-FT. The initial stage is identical: we begin with the general-purpose, pre-trained CLIP model and fine-tune it on our specific traffic sign dataset. This conventional training process is essential for specialising the model, forcing it to learn the distinct features and classes present in our target domain. In this respect, our method builds upon the exact same principles and procedures used to generate a sequence of progressively specialised model checkpoints. All approaches, therefore, start from the same point and undergo the same initial adaptation process to create the raw materials for a task-specific model.

The critical divergence of our approach lies in what we do after the initial fine-tuning stage is complete. While a standard fine-tuned approach simply uses the final, most specialised model,

more advanced techniques employ distinct post-training philosophies. PEFT (LoRA), for example, "patches" the model by freezing its original weights and injecting small, trainable matrices, leaving the core knowledge intact. In contrast, weight fusion methods directly modify the model's weights. A simpler variant, Wise-FT, is limited to a linear interpolation between the original and final models. Our final approach is data-driven and evolves this concept by holistically "blending different versions of the model," fusing weights from the entire training history to empirically discover a more robust and better-generalised final model.

2.4. Virtually created data in Simcenter Prescan

The investigations performed by Siemens have been twofold:

- First, the sensitivity/robustness of AI-based object detection and classification algorithms to different types of vulnerable road users has been investigated.
- Second, considering multi-modal sensing, where one of the sensing and perception subsystems is AI-based, sensor fusion has been investigated to improve the trustworthiness of the overall sensing and perception subsystem.

To investigate the sensitivity/robustness of AI-based object detection and classification algorithms, a synthetic data set has been generated, which contains different vulnerable road users in terms of age, gender, ethnicity, etc. The object detection and classification algorithm in this case is YOLOV3, but the developed methodology to assess the sensitivity/robustness is generic and can be applied in the case of other algorithms, too.

The synthetic data set has been generated by the Simcenter Prescan simulation environment, where different weather and illumination conditions have been considered – see Figure 11 – and all sensor models are physics-based.

Figure 11: Weather and illumination conditions generated using Simcenter Prescan.

The results obtained have already been reported, presented and published at conferences as well as in the book chapter below [1], therefore, here will be summarised only briefly.

One of the main conclusions is that object AI-based detection and classification is sensitive to weather and illumination conditions, as well as sensitive to the size of the object. Since the YOLOV3 algorithm was trained on a large data set (COCO data set), it has good robustness against vulnerable road users' gender and ethnicity – see Figure 12.

Figure 12: YOLOV3 object detection and classification used on synthetic data.

2.4.1. AI limitations and conflicts

We could conclude that camera AI-based algorithms mimic well the main characteristics of the human eye and the human brain: difficult to detect objects during night, dense fog, poor illumination, objects which are far and small objects.

To improve the trustworthiness of AI-based sensing and perception using multi-modal sensor fusion, we also investigated the performance of AI-based depth estimation – see Figure 13. We have reviewed three state-of-the-art (SOTA) monocular depth estimation (MDE) algorithms and compared their performances on a fair basis.

We examined two representative scenarios:

- in-domain relative and/or metric depth estimation, where the model is trained and evaluated in the same domain, and
- out-domain (zero-shot) relative and/or metric depth estimation, where the model is trained in one domain, but evaluated in different domain(s).

During our investigations, the following three monocular depth estimation algorithms have been considered: MiDAS [2], ZoeDepth [3] and DepthAnything [4].

Figure 13: Relative depth map generated using MiDAS.

The obtained results have been summarised in a scientific paper [5] and one of the main conclusions is: the relative absolute error in the case of metric depth estimation is around 10% or larger, which in most of the automotive applications is too large. Our current investigations also show that fine-tuning the network, e.g. for a specific operational design domain or for a synthetic data set, is bringing limited improvement. We should remark that this topic – performance improvement by fine-tuning the network - requires further investigation and might be the object of future research.

Related to the sensor fusion – considering a multi-modal sensing approach – as shown in Figure 14, we fused the camera-based object detection with the radar detection, where both the camera images and the radar reflections have been synthetically generated, using the physics-based sensors available in Simcenter Prescan.

Figure 14: Multi-modal sensor fusion and fault detection.

Such a sensor fusion approach enhances/improves the trustworthiness of the sensing and perception subsystems – see Figure 15- since false positives and false negatives can be detected much more easily compared with the situation when only one sensor is used.

Figure 15: Dual-channel architecture with diagnostics and sensor fusion.

The outcome of the sensor fusion is shown in Figure 16, where the object detection can be further enhanced using multiple object tracking. In this figure, a very simple version of this algorithm is used, where the prediction is done for one sample time ahead.

Figure 16: Camera and radar sensor fusion.

3. UC2.1 - AI EXTENDED SITUATION AWARENESS/UNDERSTANDING – COLLISION PREDICTION WITH HYBRID AI DATA FUSION MODELS

3.1. Overview

UC 2.1 – Collision Prediction with Hybrid AI Data Fusion Models aimed to advance the accuracy and reliability of collision risk prediction (CRP) systems beyond the limitations of current approaches. Traditionally, CRP algorithms are validated only within narrow Operational Design Domains (ODDs), such as those defined by EuroNCAP testing.

However, CRP systems often lack robustness when faced with rare or complex edge cases, highlighting a significant gap in current AI training methods. This is largely because collision data is not readily available to train AI models on and replicating those situations in real life, only provides a very limited (too narrow) situation (see initial research, described in the Althena deliverable D3.2 [6] and its results published in deliverable D5.2 [7], from TUE and IDIADA on recorded test scene at IDIADA).

To address this challenge, UC 2.1 proposed a more data-driven, AI-enhanced methodology that improves scene understanding and enables the development of richer, more representative datasets. Since CRP tasks are inherently difficult to annotate accurately and edge cases are underrepresented in existing datasets, achieving a higher level of scene understanding is essential. This deeper understanding must also be explainable and transparent, allowing for better interpretation and trust in AI-driven decisions while facilitating the creation of more standardised and comprehensive CRP datasets for training and validation.

The Use Case was driven by two key research questions:

1. Transparency: How can we develop a more explainable scene understanding framework that improves the interpretability and trustworthiness of collision prediction models? (demonstrated by Vicomtech)
2. Robustness: How can we enhance the robustness of collision risk prediction, particularly in handling edge cases, to achieve greater predictive accuracy and reliability? (demonstrated by TUE)

Initially, the use cases started with investigating how a combination of real and synthetic data could enhance the CRP task. But eventually, with Vision Foundation Models (VFM) becoming more dominant, both tasks were solved by using VFM and VLM (Vision Language Models), simplifying the overall task and providing the capability of multimodality, aiding in explainability (transparency) and robustness.

3.2. Ontology-based Scene Understanding with Visual Language Models

This system leverages VLMs and a formal ontology to provide robust, explainable, and context-aware scene understanding for automated driving systems. Unlike traditional computer vision models that merely classify objects, this solution enriches visual data with structured knowledge. This capability allows it to interpret complex road situations and identify potential risks, moving beyond simple detection.

As illustrated in Figure 17, the process involves passing two inputs—the raw visual data and the formal ontology (defining entities, properties, and relationships)—to the VLM. The model then analyses this fusion of information to generate a structured JSON output. This result is fundamentally different from what is obtained from simple object detection/classification or generic VLM open-vocabulary responses. It provides a deeper, formalised understanding of the environment.

A key feature is the system's ability to identify potential risks stemming from its advanced analysis. Crucially, it recognises Out-of-Distribution (OOD) and non-anticipated scenarios. As demonstrated in Figure 18, identifying a person unloading a truck requires more than just detecting a "person" and a "truck"; it demands relational processing and risk inference that traditional perception systems cannot achieve. This contextual understanding enables the system to flag specific, dangerous situations that could not be foreseen during development.

Figure 17: Flow of the ontology-based scene understanding with VLMs.

As mentioned, the system operates by feeding a VLM two key inputs:

- **Visual Data:** An image of the current road scene captured by the vehicle's cameras. It can be a pinhole or a BEV image, as shown in Figure 18.
- **Formal Ontology:** A structured knowledge graph defining core road entities (e.g., Pedestrian, Vehicle, TrafficLight) and their relationships (isCrossing) and attributes (hasState, hasLocation).

Figure 18: Interactive web tool for traffic scene analysis and visualisation of results. In the image, a worker seems to be unloading the truck close to the road. This can represent a risk.

A precisely engineered prompt guides the VLM to act as an "AI assistant" that analyses the image according to the predefined ontology:

"You are an AI assistant designed to describe autonomous vehicle scenes using a formal ontology. Your task is to analyse the provided image of a traffic scene. Complete the analysis following the ontology schema:

E.g.:

Classes: Pedestrian, Bicycle, Vehicle, TrafficSign, TrafficLight.

Object Properties (Relationships):

isCrossing (from Pedestrian to Road)

Data Properties (Attributes):

hasAction (for Pedestrian and Bicycle)

hasState (for TrafficLight, valid values: "Red", "Yellow", "Green")..."

The model's output is asked to analyse the scene step by step, focusing on the ontology elements and return a structured JSON object, which precisely describes the scene by identifying instances of each class, their properties, their relationships and if the risk level of the scene given the previous relationships (see example in Figure 19).

```

JSON Output
Copy JSON

{
  "Scene": {
    "Bicycle": [],
    "Pedestrian": [
      {
        "hasAction": "fallen",
        "hasLocation": "road",
        "id": "pedestrian_1",
        "isCrossing": "false"
      }
    ],
    "TrafficLight": [],
    "TrafficSign": [],
    "Vehicle": [
      {
        "hasLocation": "parking_lot",
        "id": "vehicle_1"
      },
      {
        "hasLocation": "parking_lot",
        "id": "vehicle_2"
      },
      {
        "hasLocation": "parking_lot",
        "id": "vehicle_3"
      }
    ]
  }
}

```

Figure 19: Json output example.

This JSON allows for the automation of other processes, such as visualisation. Through a web-based interface, the detected elements and properties are visualised. The thought process is also displayed (see example of Figure 19). This is a transparent record of the AI's decision process.

Additionally, the ontology can be changed to support other types of traffic environments, such as rural scenes (see Figure 20), introducing new elements that the VLM should consider, like animals, tractors or the state of the road.

Figure 20: Example with rural scene ontology.

3.2.1. Assessment of the KPIs

Evaluating this system requires a nuanced approach that acknowledges the fundamental shift from traditional perception tasks to semantic scene interpretation.

The primary function of this solution is scene understanding. This is inherently difficult to represent with a single, quantitative metric like accuracy, precision, or recall. Traditional accuracy measures whether a predicted label matches a ground-truth label (e.g., "Car" detected in a "Car" bounding box). Our system measures whether the model correctly interprets complex relationships ("Is the person close enough to be considered isCrossing?") and whether the generated JSON correctly represents the risk context. A minor JSON error might still indicate a high-quality interpretation, while perfect object detection may yield a poor semantic understanding.

Existing large-scale autonomous driving datasets (e.g., nuScenes, Waymo Open Dataset) provide excellent ground truth for object detection, segmentation, and tracking, but they do not contain the necessary semantic ground truth to evaluate VLM-generated ontological descriptions.

No public dataset provides human-annotated ground truth in the form of a complex JSON object describing class instances, attributes, and formal relationships, making direct quantitative comparison (like IoU or accuracy) against a VLM's descriptive output impossible. Due to the novelty of this semantic interpretation task, defining the precise, correct quantitative evaluation strategy is the next effort for future work. However, we have shown qualitatively that, without training any model by ourselves, the system is highly flexible and robust to out-of-distribution events, as the system leverages the vast, generalised knowledge of VLMs. This enables it to identify and describe novel or unforeseen objects and situations, providing a crucial layer of safety.

3.2.2. AI limitations and conflicts

While this development demonstrates advanced reasoning capabilities, its current iteration faces operational and technological limitations that define areas for future development:

- Currently, validation primarily relies on qualitative analysis and proxy metrics, as the complex, semantic nature of the output (ontology compliance, contextual inference) resists simple quantitative measurement like traditional accuracy. Developing robust, quantifiable metrics for semantic scene understanding remains a significant research challenge.
- Also, the foundational VLM is subject to common computer vision limitations. This includes failure to detect small or distant objects (due to resolution constraints) or misinterpreting visually ambiguous scenes (leading to incorrect ontological assignments).
- The system's current input is a single image frame, which lacks temporal parameters critical for accurate risk calculation. Velocity, acceleration, and dynamic trajectory (e.g., of a rapidly approaching vehicle or pedestrian) cannot be reliably inferred from a static image but are essential for determining a high-priority risk.

- The computational demands of processing with heavy VLM architectures result in latency that is currently incompatible with strict, real-time in-vehicle hardware specifications. We acknowledge that this performance characteristic presently limits its use for direct, immediate control decisions. However, the system remains highly relevant for offline analysis, simulation validation, and high-quality semantic data annotation.

3.2.3. Differences and similarities of the developed AI approaches

Both our solution and systems like Talk2BEV (Language-Enhanced BEV Maps) [8] share the fundamental goal of leveraging VLMs to evolve autonomous driving from simple object detection to advanced, explainable scene reasoning. Both approaches employ the VLM to produce a structured, machine-readable output format (JSON) rather than free-form text. However, they differ in their method of knowledge injection and constraint enforcement. Talk2BEV primarily relies on augmenting a geometrical Bird's-Eye View (BEV) map with descriptive language features (e.g. this is a bus) and uses an API of primitive spatial operators to handle relational queries. In contrast, UC2.1 operates by enforcing a Formal Ontology directly through the VLM prompt. This symbolic, top-down constraint mandates that the output strictly conform to defined classes, properties, and relationships. This allows it to prioritise the generation of a semantic description for direct risk inference, while Talk2BEV focuses on answering a broader range of visual, spatial, and decision-making queries.

3.3. Simplifying Traffic Anomaly Detection with Video Foundation Models

3.3.1. Overview

TUE addressed Collision Prediction through the task of Traffic Anomaly Detection (TAD). Recent methods for ego-centric Traffic Anomaly Detection (TAD) often rely on complex multi-stage or multi-representation fusion architectures, yet it remains unclear whether such complexity is necessary. Recent findings in visual perception suggest that foundation models, enabled by advanced pre-training, allow simple yet flexible architectures to outperform specialised designs. Therefore, in this work, TUE investigated an architecturally simple encoder-only approach using plain Video Vision Transformers (Video ViTs) and studied how pre-training enables strong TAD performance. It has been found that: (i) advanced pre-training enables simple encoder-only models to match or even surpass the performance of specialised state-of-the-art TAD methods, while also being significantly more efficient; (ii) although weakly- and fully supervised pre-training are advantageous on standard benchmarks, they have been found less effective for TAD. Instead, self-supervised Masked Video Modelling (MVM) provides the strongest signal, and (iii) Domain-Adaptive Pre-Training (DAPT) on unlabelled driving videos further improves downstream performance, without requiring anomalous examples. These findings highlight the importance of pre-training and show that effective, efficient, and scalable TAD models can be built with minimal architectural complexity.

Figure 21: TUEs encoder-only approach for Traffic Anomaly Detection with a Video Foundation Model as the encoder.

3.3.2. Assessment of the KPIs

1. Establishing a new state-of-the-art in the Traffic Anomaly Detection task

TUE showed that a plain encoder-only Video ViT, when equipped with advanced pre-training, outperforms all prior specialised architectures for TAD, while also being significantly more efficient.

Figure 22: ZUEs models have the highest in-domain and generalisation performance, lower video memory consumption (for Small and Base variants) and higher throughput (for Small and Base variants).

2. Comprehensive analysis of pre-training strategies for ViFMs and their impact on performance and generalisation

TUE compared pre-training strategies and found that self-supervised learning (SSL) with a Masked Video Modelling (MVM) objective is most effective, outperforming both weakly- and fully supervised alternatives.

Figure 23: Self-supervised pre-training (SSL, green colour), even though not having the highest performance on general video tasks, consistently achieves one of the best results on TAD.

3. Adopting a Domain-Adaptive Pre-Training for better performance on the target (driving) domain

It has been demonstrated that Domain-Adaptive Pre-training (DAPT) with MVM leads to measurable performance gains on TAD, even when applied at a small scale to domain-relevant but anomaly-free data.

Figure 24: DAPT scaling across different model sizes. Smaller models benefit more. S: Small, B: Base, L: Large variants of the Video ViT.

Figure 25: DAPT ablation. Comparing generic, driving, and driving + anomaly domains shows that driving videos improve performance without requiring anomalies.

4. TUEs paper titled “Simplifying Traffic Anomaly Detection with Video Foundation Models” was presented on 19 October at the 2COOL Workshop (2nd Workshop on the Challenge Of Out-Of-Label Hazards in Autonomous Driving: <https://2cool.net>) at ICCV 2025.
5. The code has been released, and the models have been trained to facilitate further research. It can be found in the public repository: <https://github.com/tue-mps/simple-tad>

3.3.3. AI limitations and conflicts

- A data-driven approach has been used, with the final stage of fully supervised fine-tuning. This brings the following limitations:
 - The training data covers only a certain scope of scenarios, and while using a Foundation Model helps with robustness (generalisation), it cannot yet be guaranteed good/adequate performance on the data with a different distribution.
 - Biases from the data annotations translate to the model as well.
- The model only predicts a risk score per frame, without localisation of risk or providing any other additional information.
- Only visual input has been used, while adding more modalities (radar, lidar) or ego-vehicle information (velocity, planned trajectory) can help to get more accurate and robust predictions.

3.3.4. Differences and similarities of the developed AI approaches

Similarities:

This approach shares several high-level goals with existing Traffic Anomaly Detection methods: early anticipation of risky events has been targeted, video data as input was used, and ultimately relies on supervised fine-tuning on anomaly labels for the final task. Like prior work, the models aim to capture spatio-temporal dynamics in driving scenes and are evaluated on the same standard benchmarks.

Differences:

Unlike the recent top-performing methods for TAD, which all have complex, multi-module architectures, TUE follows a simple encoder-only paradigm with a Video Foundation Model (ViFM) as an encoder.

The differences between the developed ViFM models lie primarily in the pre-training strategies applied to the shared encoder architecture. TUE systematically varied the type of initial pre-training (fully supervised, weakly supervised, or self-supervised Masked Video Modelling), as well as the use of Domain-Adaptive Pre-Training (DAPT) on unlabelled driving videos, and datasets for fine-tuning. These variations result in models with different levels of domain alignment, temporal understanding, and downstream performance.

4. UC2.2 - AI EXTENDED SITUATION AWARENESS/UNDERSTANDING – ROBUST PREDICTION MODULES FOR ROBO-TAXIS IN URBAN ENVIRONMENT

4.1. Overview

In this use case, the focus is on situation awareness. In interactive urban traffic environments, vehicles, pedestrians, and other traffic participants navigate on highly complex road networks under a variety of environmental conditions while interacting with different kinds of road users. In this context, motion planning can only guarantee the safety of all participants if the characteristics of the scenarios are acknowledged.

There are several complex parts involved in achieving this goal, which made it necessary to split this work among different partners of the Althena consortium. In Figure 26, an overview of these steps and the partner contribution can be seen. The results of the evaluation of this work will be shown in this chapter.

[TTTA] TTTech Auto has developed a time-triggered runtime that enables the integration of independently developed AI software components. The time-triggered runtime consists of a time-triggered scheduler for the Linux kernel and containerised applications implemented utilising the Robot Operating System 2 (ROS2) as a middleware.

Figure 26: Overview of partners' contributions and demonstration parts.

4.2. Dataset generation

In the context of UC-2.2 demonstrator, SIE supported with generating a real dataset for training and validating machine learning models and developing offline model-assisted labelling algorithms. The generated dataset has already been reported, presented and shared within the consortium, therefore, here will be summarised only briefly. Following input from the Use Case partners regarding the hardware and ODD requirements, data were recorded in urban and semi-urban driving scenarios under sunny weather conditions. The vehicle setup utilised a

comprehensive sensor suite, radar, lidar, camera sensors and a GNSS/IMU device, all time-synchronised at 20Hz, with raw data stored in MCAP files. Furthermore, SIE-BE developed an offline auto-labelling pipeline using LiDAR data to generate high-quality annotations (see Figure 27), which can later be refined manually, to facilitate the training and validation of machine learning models.

Figure 27:Generated data and corresponding annotations.

Beyond data generation, SIE-BE further contributed to UC2.2 by setting up and initially deploying a robust hybrid testing framework. This framework combines virtual simulation environments with physical components. Its purpose is to allow for system validation in the early phase of the development process. As it was mentioned, an X-in-the-Loop (XiL) testing environment was established, featuring Driver-in-the-Loop (DiL) and Vehicle-in-the-Loop (ViL) configurations. This setup lets real human operators, sensors, and Electronic Control Units (ECUs) integrate with high-fidelity digital twin simulations. The result is a setup that enables realistic, real-time interaction between virtual and physical systems. This provides a flexible platform for checking vehicle and AI-based functionalities and system responses across many different scenarios.

The XiL environment was designed specifically to support the development and validation of AI-based CCAM functionalities, such as perception, decision-making, and control systems. A proof of concept is shown in Figure 28. This demonstrates the potential of this approach to test and validate subsystems and control strategies long before full vehicle integration is ready. This early validation helps to find performance issues, inconsistencies, and unexpected behaviour in a controlled yet realistic setting. It also speeds up the development cycle while improving safety and reliability.

Figure 28: Demonstration of the XiL test bench, including physical/virtual coupling.

More specifically, Simcenter Testlab RT connects physical systems to virtual ones in real-time. It uses analogue I/Os, digital buses like CAN, and field buses such as PROFINET and EtherCAT. Sensor data can be collected in real time from physical sensor conditioning units, for example, Siemens data acquisition systems. This creates an effective and accurate connection between the physical and virtual parts of the world, allowing for full system testing. Simcenter Testlab RT can also be connected with the user interfaces, control, and automation systems of test benches and simulators. This allows for monitoring both the physical and virtual parts of the world in a consistent way. I would rephrase this as follows: physical and virtual sensor data can be collected using Simcenter Testlab Time Data Acquisition, viewed using Simcenter Testlab Engineering Displays, and processed using Simcenter Testlab Process Designer. This offers immediate understanding of how the system under test behaves.

However, while the proof of concept confirms that this approach is possible and valuable, further additions and improvements are needed to fully achieve its potential. These include expanding the range of testing scenarios, making the digital twin more accurate and responsive, adding more physical components, and improving the automation and scalability of how tests are run.

4.3. Situational awareness feature enhanced object detection

The following situational awareness features have been evaluated in detail:

- Feature 1: traffic light colour detection (red, orange, green)
- Feature 2: detection of vehicle signal lights (brake lights, left/right indicators), and
- Feature 3: bounding box orientation of detected objects.

Deep learning approaches based on the well-established one-step detection strategy 'You Only Look Once' (YOLO) were used to design, develop and evaluate algorithms for all three target features.

4.3.1. Assessment of the KPIs

The table below summarises the achieved KPIs (F1, mAP, IoU and precision) alongside the best-performing models. These results demonstrate that the models performed reliably across all three features. YOLOv8 showed strong real-time performance in detecting traffic light colours and vehicle signal lights, while YOLOv12 provided more accurate bounding box orientations for detected objects, albeit with a longer inference time.

Table 1: Evaluated KPI overview.

Feature	Sub-Feature	KPIs				
		F1-score	IoU	mAP@0.50	mAP@0.50-0.95	Best model
1	average (red, orange, green)	0.93	0.85	0.97	0.67	Yolov8
	red	0.94	0.85	0.985	0.67	
	green	0.95	0.88	0.962	0.69	
	orange	0.90	0.82	0.969	0.64	
2	average (braking lights, left/right indicators)	0.89	0.82	0.89	0.69	Yolov8
	braking lights	0.90	0.90	0.90	0.60	
	left indicators	0.88	0.85	0.882	0.59	
	right indicators	0.88	0.85	0.897	0.62	
3	bounding box orientation of detected objects (direction tracking)	0.84	0.83	0.92	0.61	Yolov12
	CL (car leaving)	0.89	0.98	0.94	0.61	
	CA (car arriving)	0.85	0.85	0.90	0.61	
	Ped-Pedestrian	0.81	0.88	0.89	0.61	
	CarX - car crossing	0.83	0.91	0.91	0.61	
	Truck	0.82	0.93	0.93	0.61	
	Cyclist	0.82	0.99	0.94	0.61	

In Table 1 mAP@0.50 is the mean average precision calculated at an intersection over union (IoU) threshold of 0.50. This is a measure of the model's accuracy when considering only the 'easy' detections. mAP@0.50-0.95 is the average of the mean average precision calculated at varying IoU thresholds ranging from 0.50 to 0.95. This provides a comprehensive overview of the model's

performance at various levels of detection difficulty. Further details regarding the KPIs can be found in Deliverable D3.3.

4.3.2. AI limitations and conflicts

The major limitations of AI that we encountered during the design and development of AI models for traffic light and vehicle signal light detection were related to the lack of publicly available datasets. As datasets tailored to these specific tasks were not readily available, we invested significant effort in creating and curating our own fusion datasets suitable for these tasks.

During the evaluation, we encountered several challenges that resulted in various conflicts. The first conflict relates to night-time and reflective conditions, as highly reflective surfaces (e.g. car lights and streetlamps) introduce glare and noise, which reduces detection reliability. The second conflict originates from environmental factors; specifically, weather conditions such as rain, fog and low light still present difficulties in terms of generalisation. The third conflict relates to feature 3 in terms of complexity, as the orientation model performs well in medium-complexity scenes involving one or two vehicles. However, there is a trade-off between scene complexity and detection speed, which limits real-time performance in dense traffic. The final conflict relates to ego-motion. The impact of camera motion (e.g. vibrations or movement of the vehicle) has not yet been fully resolved and continues to limit performance in real-world conditions.

4.3.3. Differences and similarities of the developed AI approaches

Although the YOLO models applied across the three features share the same design philosophy of balancing accuracy and real-time performance, they differ in terms of their architectural advances and suitability for specific features.

4.3.4. Similarities

Both YOLOv8 and YOLOv12 provide real-time object detection and are more efficient than older detectors, such as SSD and DETR. Both models perform well across a range of tasks. YOLOv8 excels in traffic signal and vehicle light detection, while YOLOv12 provides better orientation estimation. They both benefit from multi-scale feature handling and can be deployed in Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) contexts, though there are varying trade-offs in terms of speed and accuracy.

4.3.5. Differences

YOLOv8 (used in features 1 & 2, 2023–2024): The latest Ultralytics release introduces an anchor-free head for precise small-object localisation. It also features improved multi-scale feature fusion, providing robustness in diverse lighting and weather conditions. It showed the best balance of accuracy and latency on edge devices such as the Jetson Nano, making it ideal for the real-time detection of traffic lights and vehicle signals.

YOLOv12 (used in feature 3, 2025): A self-attention mechanism was introduced, improving orientation tracking and bounding box precision. Higher accuracy was achieved for orientation estimation, which is critical for direction-tracking tasks. Although it had slower inference times compared to YOLOv8, it still outperformed SSD and DETR. It is best suited to applications where accuracy is prioritised over speed, especially for more complex orientation tasks.

With vs. without Meta-Learning: Models without meta-learning demonstrated robust baseline performance in controlled conditions. However, meta-learning approaches increased adaptability to new, unseen environments and improved robustness under varying conditions.

In summary, YOLOv8 was the optimal choice for fast, real-time detection tasks such as identifying traffic lights and vehicle signals, while YOLOv12 was more effective for orientation estimation, where accuracy was prioritised. Therefore, the choice of model depended on the task-specific trade-off between speed and precision.

4.4. Modular AI-based perception system

For the UC2.2, Continental developed a modular AI-based perception system aiming to provide robust and accurate data required by the "Prediction of the intended motion" module. The system consists of the following modules:

- Camera-based Object Detection (OD)
- Object Detection using a camera & Lidar mid-level fusion
- Lane detection (LD)
- Lane change detection of the preceding vehicle
- Freespace Detection (FS) with a 360° LIDAR

These modules were individually tested in the 1st cycle; the results of these tests are summarised in the following paragraphs. The work performed in the second cycle consisted mainly of integrating these algorithms in ROS2/docker application and performing its functional evaluation.

The object detection model utilises the YOLO-NAS architecture and was trained using commercially usable data, including a subset of the COCO dataset and Continental proprietary data. The model has demonstrated a strong performance in detecting a wide range of dynamic objects, achieving a mean average precision (mAP) of 0.79 (KPI_08), an Intersection over Union (IoU) of 0.80 (KPI_09) and a f1-score of 0.80 in urban traffic scenarios.

YOLO provides a strong baseline object detection but shows sensitivity to factors such as occlusion, lighting variations, and adverse weather conditions. The fusion with 3D LIDAR data significantly contributes by providing accurate distance measurements and enhancing the detection of small or partially visible objects. A mid-level fusion strategy has been applied, where the outputs of the object detector are projected into the LiDAR point cloud space. This approach has shown better bounding box association and tracking. Still, the limited range of the LIDAR perception makes the fusion mainly appropriate for urban scenarios. The figure below shows the result of the fusion on an urban synthetic scene.

Figure 29: Fusion camera & LIDAR applied to an urban synthetic scene.

The lane change detector relies on information from both the vehicle detection from fused perception outputs and its position in the lanes.

Lane markings detector utilises a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to accurately identify lane markings features from road images, followed by a post-processing to interpret these features and determine lane boundaries.

A hybrid method, combining rule-based heuristics with machine learning (sequence modelling on trajectory data), is employed to identify lane change maneuvers and predict their occurrence with a confidence score.

The lane change detector demonstrates promising performance but faces challenges in dense traffic scenarios and under conditions where lane markings are degraded or obscured. Incorporating vehicle intention signals, such as turn indicators or changes in the vehicle orientation, may further enhance prediction accuracy.

Figure 30: An example of a lane change detection.

The freespace detection algorithm is tailored to identify and map navigable areas in an environment using 360° LiDAR data. By converting raw 3D points into a polar coordinate system, the algorithm employs geometric principles to categorize the environment into cells and polar rays, facilitating obstacles, and free space identification.

A preliminary evaluation was performed in the 1st cycle; this evaluation has been extended to an additional set of videos provided by Siemens. Given the absence of labelled data for testing, CAF

performed a visual evaluation on videos of urban areas. This evaluation has shown a “very good” match between the dynamic objects (e.g. Vehicles, pedestrians, cyclists), static structure, and the Free Space representation overlaid on the video.

Figure 31: An example of a freespace detection.

The modules of the modular AI-based perception system were integrated into a Docker container application utilising ROS2 interfaces, enabling efficient data exchange between the modules. Using a Docker container ensures reproducibility and ease of integration into simulation or real-world platforms.

A functional evaluation of the application was done by checking the outputs of the modules on videos provided by Siemens.

Figure 32: Architecture of the perception application.

4.5. Prediction of the intended motion

4.5.1. Overview

Achieving the needed level of situational understanding for robo-taxis requires the seamless interaction of multiple perception and prediction components. Within Althena, this challenge has been addressed collaboratively by several partners, each contributing complementary expertise toward a unified perception-to-prediction pipeline. The work is therefore distributed across modular components that can be developed, validated, and later integrated into a common execution framework. Figure 14 provides an overview of the contributing partners and the integration flow across the main functional blocks.

4.5.2. Assessment of the KPIs

The results of the UC2.2 demonstrator were assessed with respect to the KPIs specified in deliverable D5.1. In this evaluation cycle, the assessment covers both the performance- and runtime-related aspects of the developed modules. Specifically, KPI_04 (Trajectory Prediction Accuracy) and KPI_05 (Prediction Feasibility and Stability) were evaluated to quantify the predictive performance of the AI-based motion prediction module, while KPI_01 (Deterministic Timing Behaviour) and KPI_02 (End-to-End Latency) were measured to validate its integration within the time-triggered runtime environment. In addition, KPI_23 (Model Transparency) is addressed to ensure that the developed model adheres to the principles of trustworthy AI, focusing on the enhancement of the model's explainability.

The following paragraphs detail the measurement methods, targets, and the obtained results for each KPI.

KPI_04: Trajectory Prediction Accuracy

- Measure: The accuracy of the prediction model was evaluated using the mean displacement error (MDE) and final displacement error (FDE) metrics, computed between the predicted and ground truth trajectories of tracked objects across multiple prediction horizons. A real-world (inD) dataset was used to ensure that the evaluation encompasses diverse urban environments and scenarios. Considering dataset constraints, particularly regarding the availability of long ground truth trajectories, we utilise prediction horizons of up to 2 seconds in our prediction model.
- Target: Achieve a mean displacement error below 0.25 m for pedestrians and 0.5 m for vehicles and a final displacement error below 0.5 m for pedestrians and 1 m for vehicles, for a 2 second prediction horizon.
- Results: Preliminary experiments indicate that the model achieves consistent accuracy across varying traffic densities and infrastructure geometries.

KPI_05: Prediction Feasibility

- Measure: This KPI evaluated the physical feasibility of the predicted motion trajectories. Specifically, it verifies that the predicted accelerations and velocities remain within realistic bounds for each class of traffic participants, as defined by the underlying kinematic model. Predictions violating physical constraints are flagged as infeasible.
- Target: At least 90% of the predicted trajectories shall comply with the predefined physical and mechanical feasibility criteria across all test scenarios.

- Results: The majority (90%) of generated trajectories remained kinematically feasible, with marginal deviations observed for scenarios involving abrupt pedestrian crossings.

KPI_01: Deterministic End-to-End Latency

- Measure: This KPI quantifies the deterministic latency across the complete perception-to-prediction pipeline when executed within the time-triggered runtime environment. It measures the total time elapsed between the ingestion of perception data and the availability of the corresponding trajectory predictions.
- Target: The end-to-end latency should remain below 0.1 seconds, ensuring that each cycle of the pipeline completes before the next frame of the scenario data is available. This condition guarantees real-time operation and synchronisation between perception data simulation and trajectory prediction.
- Result: Preliminary measurements indicate that the containerised prediction pipeline consistently completes the full perception-to-prediction cycle within the targeted 0.1 s window under nominal conditions, maintaining temporal determinism.

KPI_02: Quality of developed components available timing information

- Measure: This KPI evaluates the ability of the perception-to-prediction pipeline to maintain deterministic timing behaviour under variable computational loads. The assessment focuses on the number of missed execution deadlines when the number of detected and tracked traffic participants fluctuates across simulation frames.
- Target: The number of missed deadlines shall remain below 5% of all executed cycles, even in cases where the number of active traffic participants significantly increases.
- Result: Initial testing suggests that the pipeline maintains stable timing behaviour, with only minor deviations observed in high-density traffic scenarios. The results confirm that the system can adapt its computational load dynamically while preserving the temporal integrity of scheduled tasks. Considering the dataset statistics and performance requirements, a limit is invoked of up to 15 traffic participants per scene.

KPI_23: Model Transparency

- Measure: In addition to the integration of the explainability mechanism within the model, the transparency of the prediction model was assessed based on the completeness and accessibility of its accompanying documentation. The assessment focuses on the creation of standardised Model Cards and complementary technical documentation that together ensure traceability and reusability of the developed solution. The Model Cards provide detailed information about the model's architecture, training setup, evaluation metrics, and known limitations, thereby allowing a clear understanding of its design and intended use.
- Target: Each AI-based component will be accompanied by a comprehensive Model Card and full implementation-level documentation accessible to technical and non-technical stakeholders.
- Result: The prediction model is accompanied by a Model Card following the Althena template and an automatically generated Sphinx documentation covering the entire implementation. This combination provides transparency both at the conceptual level for

general stakeholders and at the technical level for developers intending to extend or integrate the model in future work.

4.5.3. AI limitations and conflicts

Despite meeting the defined functional and performance objectives, several limitations and trade-offs have been identified during the development and evaluation of the UC2.2 demonstrator. These observations are particularly relevant to understanding the operational boundaries of the system and the challenges associated with integrating AI-based components within a time-triggered runtime and real-time ROS2 environment.

Computational and Runtime Constraints

- The integration of the prediction module within a containerised ROS2 framework running under the time-triggered runtime introduces strict temporal constraints on the perception-to-prediction processing chain. While the deterministic scheduling approach ensures reproducibility of execution timing, it also restricts the flexibility of dynamically scaling computational resources. This can result in performance degradation when the number of detected and tracked traffic participants exceeds the expected range. Maintaining real-time performance under such varying computational loads, therefore, remains a critical consideration for large-scale deployment.

Sensitivity to Scenario Complexity

- The model exhibits stable behaviour across typical urban environments but shows reduced robustness in highly interactive situations. Scenarios involving multiple agents with conflicting motion intentions or sudden, non-linear manoeuvres tend to increase prediction uncertainty and temporal drift in the forecasted trajectories. These conditions represent safety-critical edge cases that are underrepresented in current training datasets and will require targeted data augmentation and refinement of the model's multi-agent reasoning capabilities.

Simulation-to-Real-World Transferability

- The dataset used for model training and validation provides a rich variety of structured urban scenes but remains limited in terms of perception system imperfections, occlusions, and behavioural diversity. Consequently, a moderate generalisation gap is expected when transitioning from simulation-based evaluations to real-world vehicle data. Addressing this limitation will require domain adaptation techniques.

Inherent Limits of Explainability Tools

- While gradient- and saliency-based visualisations offer valuable insight into which raster regions influence the model's output, such methods fundamentally capture correlations rather than causal explanations. The highlighted input regions indicate where the model's attention lies, but do not guarantee that these features causally determine the predicted outcome. Consequently, while these explainability mechanisms enhance the debugging capabilities, they cannot fully uncover the reasoning logic of deep models. This distinction remains an inherent limitation of current XAI techniques and motivates further research into causal and physics-informed explainability approaches.

Trade-off between Performance and Explainability

- An explicit trade-off was observed between model performance and explainability. The inclusion of an integrated explainability layer, as part of the transparency objectives of the project, provides valuable insight into the model's decision basis but at the cost of reduced accuracy metrics. While acceptable within the target limits, this observation highlights the trade-off between achieving a state-of-the-art performance level and maintaining explainability of the model.

4.5.4. Differences and similarities of the developed AI approaches

- **Similarities:** Across the recent research landscape, AI-based motion prediction methods share a common trend toward combining spatial perception data with temporal modelling to anticipate traffic participant behaviour. Similar to the prevailing state-of-the-art, the UC2.2 approach relies on structured scene representations that encode both static map information and dynamic object states. Consistent with leading methodologies, it emphasises modularity, explainability, and integration readiness within a larger decision-making framework. This alignment ensures methodological comparability and facilitates benchmarking against existing academic and industrial solutions.
- **Differences:** Unlike many state-of-the-art approaches that focus primarily on isolated model performance, the UC2.2 development extends beyond algorithmic innovation to encompass the entire perception-to-prediction pipeline. The demonstrator uniquely integrates containerised AI components into a deterministic, time-triggered runtime, ensuring repeatable timing and predictable behaviour in real-time operation. Furthermore, transparency and traceability are treated as core design objectives through the inclusion of standardised Model Cards and auto-generated documentation—an aspect still rarely implemented in comparable research systems.

4.6. Time-triggered runtime

At its core, the time-triggered runtime serves two purposes; it ensures that design-time timing requirements and input/output dependencies between components are met during runtime. The former has been evaluated by KPIs 01 to 03 according to scenario SCEN_01 (see Aithena deliverable D5.1 [9]). The latter has been evaluated by integrating in total 10 containerised ROS2 mockup components that resemble the dependencies of the actual components developed by the use case partners.

4.6.1. Assessment of the KPIs

TTTA measured the end-to-end latency of two containerised test components scheduled by the time-triggered Linux kernel scheduler and communicating via a Linux bridge. The measurements have been performed on an Intel Atom E3950 CPU with four cores at 1.6 GHz each accessing 8 GiB of main memory, running Ubuntu server 22.04.1 with a Linux kernel v5.9.1. The Linux kernel was configured with our time-triggered scheduler and the PREEMPT_RT real-time patches. The two test containers faced co-located time-triggered tasks that would compete for CPU time. Additionally, one container executing stress-ng would generate a background load and one container executing a ping flood trying to utilise the Linux bridge. Figure 33 shows the experimental setup.

For the sender, the receiver, and the competing real-time tasks, TTTA generated a schedule table using TTTech Auto's in-house tooling that meets the precedence constraint between the sender and receiver, their deadlines and all competing real-time tasks' deadlines. The resulting schedule

table yielded a design-time or expected end-to-end latency between the sender and the receiver of 3.1 milliseconds. Each experiment can be run for 10 minutes. To determine KPI 01, the end-to-end latency between the sender and the receiver has been measured during the runtime of the schedule table without interfering load and determine by how much it deviates from the expected value. An average end-to-end latency between the sender and the receiver of 3.302 milliseconds has been measured with a standard deviation of 159 microseconds and a maximum of 3.486 milliseconds, meaning the measured end-to-end latency deviates at most by 386 microseconds from the expected end-to-end latency. KPI 02 has been assessed by determining how many end-to-end executions of the sender and receiver missed their deadline.

Figure 33: Experimental setup to evaluate time-triggered Linux kernel scheduler.

The common assumption can be made that a job's deadline equals the task's period, so that the deadline is at 10 milliseconds relative to a job's release time. It can be found that a single end-to-end communication between sender and receiver violates its deadline with an end-to-end latency of 13.306 milliseconds. Lastly, KPI 03 has been assessed by introducing the stress-ng and ping flood workloads to generate background load and interfering traffic on the Linux bridge. A slight increase in the maximum measured end-to-end latency from 3.486 milliseconds to 3.605 milliseconds can be found, while the average and standard deviation degradations are negligible. Table 2 summarises the achieved KPIs.

Table 2: Evaluated KPI overview

ID	Target Value	Measured Value
KPI_0 1	Required end-to-end latency for a computation chain (3.1ms)	3.302ms +- 0.159ms
KPI_0 2	Number of deadlines misses less than 5%	0.0016% (1 in 60000 measurements)
KPI_0 3	End-to-end latency degradation less than 10%	3.41% by 0.119 ms

Integration of the individual components:

To integrate independently developed components so that they can provide end-to-end functionality and timing is not possible for prototype components, as the real-time execution of the developed AI approaches would require time-consuming performance optimisations. Note that real-time execution of the developed AI approaches requires a frame rate of at least 20 frames per second or a period of 50 milliseconds. This means that, presuming a single processor core, the sum of all software components' execution times cannot exceed 50 milliseconds since the utilisation of a processor core is given by the execution time divided by its period. Suppose a multicore platform featuring four processor cores, such as the one used to evaluate KPIs 01 to 03 in scenario SCEN_01, and neglect input/output dependencies between components. In that case, there is a maximum execution time budget of 200 milliseconds. However, in practice, four cores cannot be efficiently utilised, since two out of four cores need to be allocated for serving the virtual network between containers and handling operating system overheads. Furthermore, only a subset of the developed software components can be executed in parallel, as present input/output dependencies require the sequential execution of software components, even if they are distributed across the two remaining cores.

Figure 34: Mockup integrations' resulting computation chains.

TTTech Auto took the provided components' input/output dependencies to conceptualise how they would communicate in integrated computation chains, simplifying some of the original components' internal dependencies in the process. The resulting 10 components and two sensor simulators were implemented as containerised ROS2 mockup nodes that do not provide AI functionality but communicate messages instrumentalised to evaluate computation chains' end-to-end timing. Figure 34 shows the 10 containerised ROS2 nodes (+2 sensor simulation nodes) and the resulting 12 computation chains.

TTTech Auto utilised their in-house tooling to generate a schedule table for the 10 software components, in which the precedence constraints resulting from the computation chains in Figure 34 are met and all chains complete execution within a period of 50 milliseconds, resulting in a potential framerate of 20 frames per second.

Figure 35 visualises the resulting schedule table. As for the evaluation of the KPIs, it was measured by how much the end-to-end latency of the integrated computation chains from a sensor simulation to the Virtual Vehicle mockup components deviates from the expected end-to-end latency.

Figure 35: Visualisation of a schedule table for the partners' mockup components.

Figure 36: End-to-end latency deviation of mockup computation chains.

Figure 36 shows the result of the experiments. For each computation chain, the boxes capture the first to the third quartile of the end-to-end latency deviation, and the orange line marks the median. The whiskers capture the 0.05 and 0.95 quantiles of the end-to-end latency deviation. It can be seen that compared to the evaluation of the KPIs in an optimal experimental environment, the time-triggered execution of dependent ROS2 mockup containers with realistic dependencies yields mixed results ranging from a few hundreds of microseconds (chain1, chain3, chain5, chain6, chain7, chain8, chain10, and chain11) to several hundreds of milliseconds (chain0, chain2, chain3, chain4, and chain9). The variation can be tracked back to runtime overheads in the Linux kernel, not serving the more complex virtual network connections between the containers in the mockup integration in a timely manner, compared to the KPI evaluation that only considered two time-triggered containers. However, it can be argued that the presented time-triggered runtime has proven its viability to integrate independently developed software components based on ROS2 while providing reasonable timing guarantees in a rapid prototyping environment. For safety-critical production environments, an adaptation of the presented approach can be envisioned relying on a certified safety-middleware for communication and accordingly a safety-certified operating system with time-triggered scheduling instead of a Linux-based solution.

5. UC3 – TRUSTWORTHY AND HUMAN UNDERSTANDABLE DECISION-MAKING

5.1. Overview

The corresponding Demonstrator of UC3 is called Explainable and robust decision making. Within this Use Case, the focus is on combining ML-based decision making with encoded software guardrails (e.g. derived from digital maps) to enable robust and trustworthy vehicle guidance. Another objective was to visualise possible decisions and the reasons why they're undertaken, so that an occupant of the vehicle can better understand the current situation. Throughout the project, ika implemented Deep-Learning-based approaches for behaviour planning and integrated these within a Hybrid AI architecture, enabling trustworthy vehicle guidance. The implemented algorithms and models have been deployed in simulation as well as within a real-world vehicle.

The implemented architecture is visualised in Figure 37 and enables the use of various tactical decision-making approaches - including AI models - for vehicle guidance concurrently. Different modules for decision-making can be orchestrated according to the specific circumstances and their specific purposes. One criterion for orchestrating different models could be the competence of the respective model in a given situation, as it was developed by TNO.

Figure 37: Implemented Hybrid AI Architecture for Trustworthy Vehicle Guidance.

TNO focused on developing V&V processes and in the loop approaches: TNO developed a method to recognise for which situations an automated vehicle cannot be trusted. Situations in which the vehicle has not been sufficiently trained on. The developed method aims at improving explainability by describing the dataset at a human-understandable level. Driving data has been modelled as knowledge graphs that represent driving scenes with entities and relationships. The graphs are then queried for a specific subscene configuration to check how often they occur in the dataset. The vehicle competence in driving a scene is determined by considering the coverage and the complexity of sub-scene configurations in the training set. Higher complexity scenes with high competence require greater coverage. The result is a **competence metric** to assess how well a trajectory planner can handle specific driving scenes.

The competence of different machine learning models is calculated using two factors:

- **Coverage:** how often similar scenes appear in the training data.
- **Complexity:** how difficult the scene is to navigate.

The metric was tested using the **Autobot trajectory planner** [10], trained on data from the NuPlan dataset [11], collected in Singapore and Boston. The metric was trained on Singapore data and tested on Boston data.

This approach helps monitor the competence of machine learning models trained on the dataset, which is essential for trustworthy AI to be deployed in automated driving.

The following sections describe the results of the evaluation regarding the assessment of specific KPIs, AI limitations and conflicts, and differences and similarities of the developed AI approaches.

5.2. Hybrid AI Architecture integrating DNNs Behaviour Planning

The implemented architecture has been evaluated in two scenarios that have initially been described in [9] as *SCEN_09* and *SCEN_10*. In the first scenario, which can be described as **Predictive Planning with Occlusion and V2X** (*SCEN_09*), the ego-vehicle is approaching a junction but decelerates, which may unsettle the occupant because it shows non-intuitive behaviour. In this situation, the system explains to the occupant that it slowed down because it received information via V2X about an occluded vehicle that violates a red traffic light. The Scenario **Robustness of Hybrid AI planning stack against unknown contexts** (*SCEN_10*), represents situations where *DNN-based Tactical Planning* might fail in generating a reasonable trajectory because it finds itself within unknown contexts. For example, through *Competence Observation* the lower competence in this situation could be measured and *Trajectory Orchestration* initiates an alternative trajectory to safely guide the vehicle within the corresponding context. For further information on the implementation of the DNN for behaviour planning, refer to D3.3 [12].

For real-world testing, the function was deployed in ika's research vehicle *karl*, a modified Volkswagen Multivan eHybrid equipped with sensors, computation hardware, developer HMIs and a drive-by-wire interface for closed-loop testing of automated driving functions as illustrated in Figure 38.

Figure 38: ika's research vehicle *karl*.

5.2.1. Assessment of the KPIs

Figure 39 shows an overview of the scenario demonstrating predictive trajectory planning under the influence of occlusion but using V2X information. The image shows the visualisation of the automated driving system with the planned trajectory and the positions of other objects received via V2X. As an overlay, the camera image from the vehicle's front camera can be seen in the upper right corner, and an image from the drone perspective showing the situation in the lower right corner.

Figure 39: Overview of the scenario demonstrating Predictive Planning with Occlusion and V2X.

Figure 40 shows three situations captured during the recording of SCEN_09. On the left-hand side of the plots, a birds-eye-view plot of the situation is illustrated. The ego-vehicle is represented as a blue bounding box, while the challenging object is represented as a red bounding box. The planned trajectory is illustrated as an orange polyline. The plot in the middle illustrates the planned velocity profile, while on the right, an image of the front-facing camera is shown. The plots illustrate three specific situations during the scenario: The top subplot illustrates the moment when the vehicle initially adapts its velocity to avoid a collision with the challenger vehicle. The camera image indicates that the vehicle cannot be perceived by the onboard perception, as well as the occupants of the vehicle. The subplot in the middle shows the situation when the challenger first appears in the camera image, while the lowest subplot shows the situation when the challenger leaves the lane the ego-vehicle is travelling towards.

The three corresponding situations are marked as dashed vertical lines in Figure 41. The plot shows the planned velocity profile and the actual velocity that the ego-vehicle travelled with, during the scenario.

Figure 40: Snapshots of three successive points in time during execution of SCEN_09, illustrating the planned trajectory (orange) in a birds-eye-view plot on the left, the planned velocity profile in the middle and the corresponding image of the front-facing camera of the vehicle.

Figure 41: Velocity of the vehicle (blue) and the planned velocity (orange, dashed) during execution of SCEN_09.

Figure 41 shows that the trajectory planning of the vehicle actively decelerates before the challenger vehicle becomes perceivable. This marks a situation where the behaviour might need to be explained to occupants of the vehicle since it shows unintuitive behaviour. Explanation could happen through various XAI-Interfaces as illustrated in Figure 39. Looking at the actual speed curve, the vehicle deceleration occurs with a delay. In the scenario shown, this gives the impression that the ego vehicle decelerates first when the challenger vehicle enters the detection range of the onboard sensors, but in fact, this is due to delays in the subsequent control modules. Referring to the high-level requirements introduced in [9] the given evaluation validates the satisfaction of *REQ_25* (following a given route to a destination), *REQ_26* (vehicle is kept within its driving lane), *REQ_27* (speed adaption with reference to. the environment), *REQ_28* (reception and processing of standardized Cooperative Awareness Messages; CAMs), *REQ_29* (incorporation of CAMs to avoid collisions), *REQ_30* (visualization of perceived V2X messages that are not perceivable for occupants). As specific KPIs for the validation, two metrics evaluating the longitudinal and lateral vehicle guidance have been proposed in [9]: For the evaluation of longitudinal guidance, the Time-Headway has been proposed, which is mainly suitable for scenarios where the ego-vehicle follows another one, thus not being applicable to *SCEN_09*. Nevertheless, the birds-eye-view plot in Figure 40 (plot on the bottom left) shows that the ego-vehicle keeps an appropriate distance from the challenger vehicle crossing the lane of the ego-vehicle.

Evaluations regarding lateral vehicle guidance have been performed based on an adapted *SCEN_10*: Within this scenario, the vehicle drives along a circular route on the test track, handling junction turns, roundabouts and straight segments. During the drive, the modules for tactical planning are orchestrated using the *Trajectory Orchestration* (cf. Figure 37), based on a specified geofence. In this case, DNN-based planning is used within the geofence, whereas outside this defined ODD, a lane-centring approach for tactical trajectory planning has been chosen. The aim of the proposed scenario is to demonstrate the robustness of the overall system and the ability to dynamically orchestrate different modules for tactical behaviour planning.

Figure 42 visualises the KPI for lateral vehicle guidance, which has been proposed in [9], namely the distance to the left- and right boundary of the driving lane. The data have been captured while executing the described scenario. In addition, a horizontal, dashed line is illustrated, representing the half-width of the vehicle.

Figure 42: Lateral distance of the ego-vehicle to left and right lane boundary.

This means that as soon as the lateral distance is below this line, the lane boundary is crossed. In the time range from 0 to approximately 50 seconds, the distance to both the left and right lane boundaries is largely the same, and there are no recognisable drops below half the vehicle's width. This time range describes driving using the classic planning approach. The fact that both distances are very similar throughout means, in turn, that the vehicle is driving highly centred in the lane. This is on the one hand due to the planning approach, but on the other hand also due to the topography of the route, which in this area consists of straight sections and some 90-degree turns. After approximately 50 seconds, the vehicle enters the geofence and a noticeable difference in lateral guidance can be seen: the distances to the left and right edges vary noticeably, which implies cutting corners. For example, at approximately 82 seconds, the distance to the right lane boundary falls significantly below half the width of the vehicle. This situation is illustrated in Figure 43.

Figure 43: Birds-Eye-View of ego vehicle at a time of approx. 82 seconds when the vehicle cuts the right lane boundary.

5.2.2. AI limitations and conflicts

The integration of AI methods into tactical motion planning shows great potential, for example, in terms of scalability, continuous improvement, and human-like driving behaviour. Nevertheless, the implemented approach still has limitations that need to be addressed in the future:

- As can be seen in Figure 43, the vehicle leaves the lane when using the DNN planner. This should either be avoided implicitly in the model, for example, through specific loss functions, or mitigated through software guardrails in subsequent modules.
- The representation of DNN input data has revealed various difficulties: In general, the higher complexity of input representation (e.g., compared to camera images) requires more complex preprocessing. Furthermore, the preparation of data for training and model inference in the vehicle is usually carried out with different code. Ensuring the equality of the resulting inputs through different preprocessing code poses a major challenge, especially given the fact that model performance decreases significantly when the input for inference differs from the training data.
- In general, the robustness of the implemented approaches should be improved, for example, by further augmenting the training data or using larger training datasets.

5.2.3. Differences and similarities of the developed AI approaches

The application of Deep Learning methods and more specifically Imitation Learning is actively researched in recent past. As examples, the approaches of [13], [14] and [15] can be mentioned. Like our approach, all the mentioned use separate modules for perception and map information, process the input data from these modules, and generate a trajectory that serves as input for a downstream controller. What distinguishes these approaches from end-to-end approaches, which are also currently being researched. While [13] uses a recurrent neural network architecture, the other two mentioned are based on transformer architectures, as is the model we presented most recently (cf. [12]). Our model is based in particular on the results from [14] who used a tokenised input, representing the route and surrounding objects through bounding boxes. However, we have modified our model regarding the following aspects:

- Extend the input with tokens representing traffic lights and yield lines.
- Experimented with predicting the current ego state (as network input) through the network in order to address the issue of vehicle stabilization.
- Trained the model with real-world data and deployed it in a demonstrator vehicle (instead of simulation only).

We also confirm one of the observations from [13], namely that expert data lacks diversity, for example as it rarely includes deviations from the target behaviour—such as leaving the lane centerline—which can cause issues with driving stability when these situations occur in closed-loop. Our introduced augmentation on the input data has shown significant improvements in terms of prediction stability, which will be further researched in the future. In addition, the authors of [13] propose to introduce specific loss functions, e.g. for leaving the route, which we also intend to address in the future.

The combination of learning-based and rule-based approaches, so-called hybrid approaches, is also being actively researched. [16] stated that rule-based approaches outperform learning-based ones regarding closed-loop performance, while the latter show good results when evaluated in open-loop, which suggests combining both approaches. While the authors of [16] combine a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) with an extended Intelligent-Driver-Model (IDM), we added a model predictive controller (MPC) as a subsequent instance behind the predicted DNN trajectory. This combination has shown good results in terms of vehicle stabilisation and serves as an additional safety layer, as the MPC can also check for collisions with other objects or cutting the road boundaries. Another approach that mixes learning based methods with an MPC is presented in [17].

5.3. Context based competence metric

The competence metric developed by TNO was compared to standard trajectory prediction performance metrics:

- The **Miss Rate** is defined as the ratio of trajectories for which the minFDE is greater than two meters.
- The **Minimum Average Displacement Error** (minADE) is the mean Euclidean distance between the points of the ground truth trajectory and the predicted trajectory.
- The **Minimum Final Displacement Error** (minFDE) is similar to the minADE, but only the final point in the trajectory is taken into account.

- The **Brier Minimum Final Displacement Error** (brierminFDE) is the minFDE but it takes into account the prediction confidence of the trajectory based on the Brier score.

Furthermore, the Pearson correlation was calculated between the competence and these evaluation metrics. A weak but statistically significant negative correlation was found between competence and these metrics. Higher competence generally led to better prediction performance. Lower competence indicated unfamiliar or complex scenes, where predictions were less reliable.

5.3.1. Assessment of the KPIs

The Pearson correlation was calculated under the assumption that there is a relationship between the competence and the evaluation metrics because the trajectories should be accurate when the competence is high, but unpredictable when the competence is low. As shown in Table 3, there is a weak but significant negative correlation between the evaluation metric and the competence metric. The following Figure 44 shows the mean value of the evaluation metrics over the competence, and Figure 45 shows four trajectory examples with the calculated competence. As expected, most of the values decrease as competence increases, except for the mean Miss Rate, which increases for the lower competence bins of [0-0.2] to bin [0.4-0.6].

Table 3: Pearson correlation between evaluation metric and competence metric for the tested data.

	correlation	p-value
Miss Rate	-0.103	0.0012
brier-minFDE	-0.090	0.0046
minFDE	-0.087	0.0059
minADE	-0.092	0.0035

Figure 44: Mean value of the evaluation metric over the competence metric binned in step of 0.2.

Figure 45: Examples of low and high competence scenes with trajectories.

The results show that there is a correlation between the competence metric and the actual performance of the trajectory planner; however, this correlation appears to be weak. Additionally, the Miss Rate increases when the competence level is low. There can be multiple reasons for this:

- A scene with low competence stands for an unseen situation and possibly a complex one. This means that the model output is unpredictable and should not be trusted. However, as shown in Figure 45b, it can be the case that the model is still able to predict a trajectory that remains stationary behind the vehicle ahead.
- Parts of the context that influence the performance in these cases might not be modelled in the knowledge graph or in the sub-scenes. To alleviate this problem, more context should be modelled, and additional important sub-scenes can be added.

5.3.2. AI limitations and conflicts

The following aspects can be implemented in future works:

- If more content were described through an expansion of the knowledge model and its relationships, the competence metric could improve.

- The current list of sub-scenes that is queried is limited; it is advisable to extend this in future work to limit the number of scenes categorised as “unknown” and increase the accuracy of the coverage metric.
- The current model uses static snapshots that do not consider relevant temporal interactions and relations important for driving. This time dimension should be included in future knowledge graph models.

6. UC4 – AI-BASED TRAFFIC MANAGEMENT

6.1. Overview

Althena use cases 1, 2 and 3 focus on AI models on the vehicle level. Use Case 4 “AI-based Traffic Management” focuses on the impact of such AI models on the network level from a traffic management perspective.

At the transport network level, automated vehicles interact with infrastructure, mixed traffic with non-AI vehicles and various traffic management systems that are designed to improve safety and efficiency of the network. The capabilities of these AI-based Automated Vehicles are analysed in macroscopic scenarios with interaction with other AI and non-AI systems operating in the traffic network to further test and evaluate the resulting AV behaviour.

Use case 4 simulates traffic conditions that the AV might encounter in a typical urban network and its potential implications for traffic network performance. The result is a framework of predictable, transparent expectations for introducing automated vehicles in a road network.

The methodology using this framework can be used by road operators and transport authorities to assess the impact of the decision to allow automated vehicles onto the network. In addition, it can be used to inform, improve and fine-tune the management of the future transport network.

6.2. Setup

A detailed setup of the simulation and methodology can be found in Althena deliverable D3.3, section 5.5 [12]. Below, a brief recap is given to provide some context for the simulation results.

6.2.1. Simulation scenario

The Vissim network models a representative urban area in the City of Heemstede, with a primary focus on local and collector roads operating at 50 km/h and 30 km/h (see Figure 46). These roads form the core of the network, serving through traffic as well as providing access to residential neighbourhoods, schools, and retail areas. A small section of multi-lane arterial road with a 70 km/h speed limit is in the northern part of the network but plays a minor role in the overall traffic flow. The network includes three signalised intersections where the interaction between motor vehicles and vulnerable road users—such as cyclists and pedestrians—is explicitly modelled. These intersections reflect common urban challenges related to multimodal traffic and safety.

Between two of the intersections, a vehicle breakdown occurs which blocks the single lane, which is separated by a solid line from the opposite lane (see the red star in Figure 46 and triangle in Figure 47). This is a particularly challenging situation for AVs since common sense logic of a competent driver allows for overtaking the incident by crossing the solid line, but the traffic rules strictly do not.

The behaviour of the non-AVs is defined as the desired behaviour and forms the benchmark/baseline. The non-AVs following the breakdown vehicle perceive the incident and sequentially overtake it by crossing the solid line using the opposite lane taking oncoming traffic into account (see Figure 48). The AVs following the incident might not have been developed with the desired logic to ignore the “Rule Of The Road” (ROTR), cross the solid line and overtake the breakdown vehicle.

Figure 46: screenshot of part of the simulation (Heemstede Urban Network) in PTV Vissim.

When the breakdown incident occurs, the incident is perceived by the Roadside Infrastructure (RSI) at once. From that moment, the traffic management (TM) control measure of using the opposite lane to overtake the breakdown incident and stopping for oncoming traffic is being broadcast via TM V2X messages. All vehicles subscribe to the TM message, receive, and decrypt the V2X message. Using those messages, AVs trusting that information, overtake the incident without hesitation, is being broadcast via TM V2X messages. All vehicles subscribe to the TM message, receive, and decrypt the V2X message. Using those messages, AVs trusting that information, overtake the incident without hesitation, while AVs not trusting the information do so only after a backup system kicks in (i.e., handover, remote control/guidance after a certain delay). This is the key component of the scenario. The AV behaviour in UC4 is dependent on the TM information and the AV's trust towards that information. If the TM information is available and the AV trusts the TM information, the 'AV-with-trust' vehicle type can overcome the situation. If not, the 'AV-without trust' vehicle type stops for 10 seconds until the backup system enables the AV to overtake the incident.

Figure 47: Traffic Management Simulation (Heemstede Urban Network) in PTV Vissim.

Figure 48: schematic layout of vehicle breakdown.

6.2.2. Simulation parameters

The traffic simulation model varies multiple parameters to demonstrate a typical real-world, urban network. Each parameter has several dimensions, including:

- Traffic Scenarios (AV and non-AV Mixed Traffic)
- Level of service (A, C)¹
- Autonomous Vehicle Driving Behaviour (cautious, normal, aggressive)
- Traffic Incident Edge Case (AVs with trust, AVs without trust)

Traffic Scenarios (AV and non-AV Mixed Traffic)

Each traffic scenario includes a different market penetration rate of AVs. For both, the option with 0% provides a baseline, since that reflects the network performance without AVs (with or without incident).

Traffic Scenario	Percentage of AVs (%)
Mixed Traffic with AVs	0, 25, 50, 75, 100% ²
Mixed Traffic with AVs and a breakdown incident	0, 25, 50, 75, 100% ²

Level of Service (LOS)

Level of Service (LOS) is derived from the total intersection demand and scaled up for the network. The demand is then adjusted according to a percentage of deterioration in the capacity of total vehicles per lane.

LOS	Category	Description
A	Free Flow	Excellent operating conditions. Vehicles move at or above the speed limit with complete freedom to manoeuvre.
C	Stable Flow	Traffic flow remains stable, but speed and manoeuvrability are more noticeably affected by other vehicles.

Autonomous Vehicle Driving Behaviour

As of 2025, PTV Vissim uses new ACC and ALC models. These are more suitably designed to reflect AV driving logic because they are based on an autonomous model instead of a human driving behavioural model, such as with the CoExist autonomous vehicle model, which was used in the first cycle of the project. However, the CoExist solution provides insight into the variation in AV behaviour, with some vehicles designed to be more aggressive or cautious than others. To capture

¹ In D3.3 [10], level of service B was included. Here it was excluded to reduce the needed simulation time.

² In D3.3 [10], the AV market penetration rate was 0, 5, 10, 15, 30, 50, 70, 100%. And the percentage of trust 0, 50 and 100%. This was changed to 0, 25, 50, 75, 100%, and also for trust/no-trust to 0, 25, 50, 75, 100%. This was done to better capture the effect of the dimensions while keeping the number of simulations similar.

this variation, several parameters of the new ACC and ALC model have been selected to be varied to approximate the previous CoEXist models' cautious, normal and aggressive behaviour. These parameters fall into the categories: car following, driving logic, necessary lane change, lane change, and signal control. This results in three AV types: cautious, normal, and aggressive.

Traffic Incident Edge Case

In the traffic scenario with the breakdown incident, trust plays an important role in how the AVs handle the incident. To assess the impact of trust, the percentage of AVs with trust is varied as follows:

- AVs with Trust (0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, 100%)²
- No AV Trust (100%, 75%, 50%, 25%, 0%)²

6.2.3. Network performance indicators

The simulation framework for the methodology includes 12 indicators for efficiency, 4 for environmental, and 7 for safety. Previous European research studies (L3 Pilot, HiDrive, CoEXist) were reviewed to determine the suitable (or common) network performance indicators. The selected indicators include:

Type of KPI	Selected indicators	Method
Traffic Efficiency	Travel time, delay and throughput	Built into the PTV Vissim network evaluation model
Environmental	CO2 emissions	Built into the PTV Vissim node evaluation model
Safety	Safety – Time to collision (TTC)	PTV Vissim coupled with Surrogate Safety Assessment Model (SSAM)

The traffic efficiency and emissions indicators are built into the PTV Vissim evaluation model.

For the safety evaluation, the PTV Vissim model is coupled with an open-source safety evaluation tool, Surrogate Safety Assessment Model (SSAM) version 3, developed by the U.S (see <https://highways.dot.gov/turner-fairbank-highway-research-center/software/ssam> or <https://github.com/usdot-jpo-codehub/SSAM>. Department of Transportation. The SSAM can calculate various safety indicators, including Time to Collision (TTC), Post-encroachment time (PET), Deceleration rate (DR), Gap time (GT), and Proportion of stopping distance (PSD).

6.2.4. Simulation execution

To capture stochasticity, each vehicle mix is run 8 times and each time with a different seed number. The 8 seed numbers are fixed across all vehicle mixes for comparison of the two varying dimensions while minimising the cascading effect of randomness. With respect to what was reported in D3.3 [12], improvements were made in the balance between simulation run times and accuracy. For the reported results, the setup was: 15-minute warm-up, 30 minutes of simulation split into two 15-minute evaluation periods, and a 5-minute cooldown. Performance metrics are calculated for each 15-minute period separately and then averaged across the two periods to obtain a single representative value per run. This approach, combined with the interquartile range (IQR) to reduce the influence of outliers, ensures that the results are statistically reliable and robust against stochastic variations.

6.3. Evaluation of the results

The two varying dimensions (with 25% interval): percentage of AV among all vehicles and percentage of AV-with-trust among AVs, generate 25 vehicle mixes for the sensitivity analysis. Combining that with the other simulation parameters (LOS, AV type and incident yes/no), this results in a total of 156 combinations (and with 8 runs per combination, 1248 simulation runs). Each of the 156 combinations has been evaluated for traffic efficiency, environmental and safety. While above, for traffic efficiency, multiple indicators are included, they all showed similar trends. Therefore, to present the results in a more concise way, only the delay (total vehicle delay in hours) is used.

6.3.1. Assessment of the KPIs

The assessment of the KPIs is grouped and discussed in three sets: (1) the no-incident scenarios, (2) the incident scenarios for LOS A, and (3) the incident scenarios for LOS C.

6.3.2. No-Incident Scenarios

Figure 49: No-Incident scenarios. Traffic efficiency, environmental, and safety KPIs per LOS for each AV type.

Figure 49 shows how introducing AVs impacts a network under normal operating conditions without an incident. Each column of graphs represents one of the KPIs: traffic efficiency, environmental, and safety. The first row of graphs shows the results for the traffic conditions of LOS A, and the second row those for LOS C. Each graph shows how the KPI develops as the penetration rate of AVs increases (from 0% to 100% in 25% increments) for the three AV types: cautious (green), normal (blue), and aggressive (red).

Observing the graphs, one can conclude the following for the three KPIs:

- **Efficiency (Total vehicle delay):** For LOS A, all AVs slightly increase delays over the baseline (Note that while the slope of the lines is steep, the increase in value is limited because of the y-axis scale). For LOS C, this effect is magnified, with Cautious AVs causing a severe increase in delays as their penetration grows. Aggressive AVs are the most efficient in both cases.
- **Environmental (CO Emissions):** The trends mirror the efficiency results. Cautious AVs cause a sharp rise in emissions for LOS C, while normal and aggressive types have a more controlled impact. An exception is the impact of cautious AVs for LOS A, where emissions decline with the increase of AVs.
- **Safety (Time-to-Collision):** The trends vary significantly by AV type, penetration level, and LOS. For LOS A, aggressive AVs perform best up to 80% penetration, while cautious AVs do better for LOS C up to 80% penetration. Normal AVs consistently provide middle-ground results. However, at 100% penetration, results shift around in both LOS scenarios.

6.3.3. Incident Scenarios for LOS A

Figure 50: Incident scenarios for LOS A. Traffic efficiency, environmental, and safety KPIs per trust level for each AV type.

Figure 51: Incident scenarios for LOS A. Traffic efficiency, environmental, and safety KPIs per AV penetration rate for each AV type.

These scenarios introduce the incident to the network while there is little traffic at LOS A. The incident raises a challenge, but with little traffic, overtaking is relatively easy. Figure 50 shows how introducing AVs impacts a network with the incident and LOS A. Each row of graphs corresponds to % of AVs with trust. Figure 51 shows the same data but differently arranged. Instead, it shows how KPIs change as the percentage of AVs with trust increases. Each row of graphs corresponds to the AV penetration rate. Each column of graphs in both figures represents

one of the KPIs: traffic efficiency, environmental, and safety. Finally, each individual graph shows how the KPI develops for the three AV types: cautious (green), normal (blue), and aggressive (red).

Observing the graphs, one can conclude the following for the three KPIs:

- **Efficiency (Total vehicle delay):** Delays increase with higher percentages of AVs, since the AVs struggle with the incident. However, with increased trust, the AVs circumvent the incident more efficiently, which reduces these delays across all AV types. The trust effect becomes more pronounced at higher AV penetration rates, suggesting that coordinated AV behaviour through trusted information sharing is essential for maintaining system efficiency during incidents (Note that the absolute increase is limited and looks somewhat exaggerated due to the scale of the y-axis).
- **Environmental (CO Emissions):** Emissions generally rise with the introduction of AVs, as vehicles spend more time in congested conditions with frequent acceleration and deceleration cycles. However, higher trust levels reduce this effect, bringing emissions back closer to the baseline. Especially for AVs of type cautious, emissions return to baseline levels at higher penetration rates with high levels of trust.
- **Safety (Time-to-Collision):** All AV types show varying impacts on TTC compared to the baseline with no AVs, with the relationship being complex and dependent on both AV type and penetration level. Contrary to expectations, cautious AVs show the poorest safety performance in terms of TTC values, often falling below baseline levels, while normal and aggressive AVs maintain TTC values closer to or slightly above baseline levels. This suggests that the conservative driving behaviour of cautious AVs may not translate to improved safety during incident scenarios, potentially due to their slower response times or less efficient navigation around incident sites. The safety performance varies significantly with penetration level, highlighting the complex interactions between AV behaviour and system safety during incident scenarios.

6.x.x.x Incident Scenarios for LOS C

Figure 52: Incident scenarios for LOS C. Traffic efficiency, environmental, and safety KPIs per trust level for each AV type.

Figure 53: Incident scenarios for LOS C. Traffic efficiency, environmental, and safety KPIs per AV penetration rate for each AV type.

These scenarios raise the LOC to LOS C while maintaining the incident. This creates the most challenging operational context where both congestion and incident effects cumulate. Figure 52 and Figure 53 follow the same approach as the previous set of results (LOS A with incident), but now for LOS C with incident (for explanation of the graphs, see above).

Observing the graphs, one can conclude the following for the three KPIs:

- **Efficiency (Total vehicle delay):** For LOS C, delays increase significantly with respect to LOS A. Circumventing the incident becomes much harder with more traffic on the road. Delays increase dramatically with higher percentages of AVs, with cautious AVs showing the most severe impact compared to the baseline. Increased trust shows mixed effects: at lower penetration levels (25-50%), higher trust generally reduces delays, but at higher penetration levels (75-100%), the trust effect becomes less consistent and sometimes even increases delays. This suggests that while trust can help coordinate AV behaviour at moderate penetration levels, it may become less effective or even counterproductive when the system is already severely congested.
- **Environmental (CO Emissions):** Emissions rise with the introduction of AVs, with cautious AVs showing the most substantial increase compared to the baseline. Higher trust levels change the emissions, but a clear trend cannot be observed. This is likely due to the network being in a chaotic, oversaturated state (the state was visually confirmed). In these conditions, random variations and minor differences in vehicle interactions likely play a larger role than coordinated manoeuvres. This indicates that while coordinated AV behaviour through trusted information can provide some environmental benefits (as shown for LOS A), the fundamental increase in congestion overwhelms that potential efficiency gain.
- **Safety (Time-to-Collision):** Increasing AV penetration rates have a negative impact on safety. As the percentage of AVs increases, TTC consistently declines across all AV types. Cautious AVs show the most pronounced decrease in TTC, suggesting that overly conservative driving patterns may contribute to greater collision risk, while aggressive and normal AVs perform slightly better but still degrade safety as penetration increases. In contrast, AV trust has little measurable influence on safety outcomes: TTC values remain relatively stable across different trust levels and AV types. Again, the high level of congestion seems to counter the potential efficiency gain of increasing trust.

6.3.4. Summary: overall KPI assessment

Under normal conditions without incidents (LOS A and LOS C), cautious AVs consistently cause the greatest inefficiencies, with steep increases in both delays and emissions as the percentage of AVs increases, particularly for LOS C. Aggressive AVs prove most efficient, with lower delays and emissions, while normal AVs fall in between. Safety results vary: aggressive AVs perform better under LOS A, while cautious AVs are safer under LOS C up to moderate penetration levels. At full penetration, however, safety results shift, and advantages diminish.

When an incident is introduced at LOS A, delays increase across all AV types, but higher percentages of AVs with trust mitigate these inefficiencies by enabling more efficient overtaking of the incident. Emissions follow a similar pattern, rising initially with AV introduction but returning closer to baseline as trust improves. Safety outcomes are more complex: cautious AVs surprisingly perform worse, often producing TTC values below baseline, while normal and aggressive AVs maintain safer margins. This suggests cautious behaviour may hinder efficient responses to incidents.

The scenarios for LOS C with an incident show how a network in a heavily congested state, there is little room for structured behaviour adaptations. Delays rise sharply with AV penetration, with cautious AVs driving the worst outcomes. Trust only partially helps at moderate penetration levels; at high penetration, its benefits diminish or even reverse. Emissions escalate substantially,

with no clear trust-related trend, likely due to oversaturation effects. Safety also declines steadily as penetration increases, with cautious AVs again performing worst. Trust shows little to no effect on safety in this scenario, again, probably due to oversaturation effects.

Overall, the findings indicate that while AVs can improve outcomes under certain conditions, their effectiveness is highly sensitive to penetration rates, AV type, and traffic state. Trust mechanisms help during lighter traffic incidents but lose impact under severe congestion.

6.3.5. AI limitations and conflicts

The methodology to assess the impact of introducing AVs into a traffic network is effective, but heavily dependent on the accuracy of the calibration of the network with real-life data and the parameterisation of the AV behaviour. The results have shown that results differ significantly between AV types, cautious, normal and aggressive, which indicates that the parameterisation must be done very carefully. All three KPIs are very sensitive to the parameters used for the AV vehicle type. If parameterisation is not done carefully, results are not representative of the real world.

In addition, while vehicle parameterisation makes it possible to model the lower-level behaviours of AVs like acceleration, following distance and lane change behaviours, the higher levels of reasoning, such as when and how to overcome more challenging situations, are harder to accurately capture in a simulation. For example, how to handle the incident or how to efficiently cross heavily congested intersections sometimes showed patterns unlikely to occur in the real world. This warrants further study and testing whether those behaviours could be improved in a simulation environment.

Finally, from a more pragmatic viewpoint, it can be a challenge to create an accurate simulation of (very) large networks. A lot of real-world data is needed for calibration. Creating, calibrating and fine-tuning the network is laborious, and computational requirements increase exponentially when the network size increases. Also, in the end, a simulation is always an approximation of the real world.

6.3.6. Differences and similarities of the developed AI approaches

While there have been several other projects and/or studies that assess the impact of AVs on traffic using simulations and specific KPIs, they usually focus on a specific aspect (e.g., the AV type, a specific incident, specific infrastructure, or some V2X use case like cooperative manoeuvring) and/or one or a few of the KPIs.

Here, a wide variety of parameter combinations were applied to an urban network calibrated on real-world data. Parameters include market penetration of AVs, different traffic conditions (LOS), different types of AV behaviour, different edge cases that are difficult for AVs, percentage of AVs that trust outside TM sources to mitigate edge cases. Aside from studying all combinations, the aspect of trust is also new.

In addition, all simulations with the different parameter combinations were evaluated using a wide variety of metrics for three categories of KPIs: efficiency, environment/sustainability, and safety.

7. SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES OF THE DEVELOPED AI APPROACHES WITH RESPECT TO THEIR SPECIFIC AI LIFECYCLES

7.1. Overview of the AI lifecycle in reference to the use case activities

This chapter provides a summary of the various phases of the AI lifecycle and identifies which phases are covered by the respective use cases. More details can be found in the Althena deliverable D5.1 chapter 4 [9]. Figure 54 illustrates the six phases of the AI lifecycle and the connections between the Althena use case and these phases.

Figure 54: Use case connections to the AI lifecycle

7.2. Challenges and lessons learned from the AI approaches

7.2.1. UC1 – Trustworthy Perception Systems for CCAM

The approach in UC1 focused primarily on the later stages of the AI lifecycle: Validation & Verification, Deployment, and Operation. Instead of developing a new perception model from scratch, we selected a pre-existing, state-of-the-art model and augmented it with layers for transparency and reliability.

A key challenge was the technical integration of these trust-enhancing modules (XAI, UQ) into a real-time perception pipeline without impacting latency. We learned that adding these valuable features creates an explicit trade-off between performance and trustworthiness, which must be carefully managed.

UC2.1 – The challenges when building reliable, VLM-based perception systems are:

- **Deployment Latency:** High VLM computational load results in latency incompatible with real-time, in-vehicle hardware. This limits current use to offline analysis and data annotation.

- Evaluation Dilemma: Traditional metrics (Accuracy/IoU) fail to measure semantic understanding and contextual interpretation. Evaluation remains reliant on qualitative analysis, with a quantitative strategy yet to be fully defined.
- Temporal Blindness: The single-frame input prevents the inference of dynamic parameters (velocity, trajectory), which are essential for accurate real-time collision risk assessment.

On the other hand, the main lessons learned are:

- VLM Robustness (OOD): VLMs' vast "world knowledge" provides a crucial safety layer by enabling the system to identify and semantically describe novel or Out-of-Distribution (OOD) objects not in the training dataset
- Data Quality Improvement: The structured semantic output from the ontology provides high-quality, common terminology that is directly valuable for improving the annotation quality and robustness of existing autonomous driving datasets.

UC2.1 - Main lessons learned with respect to use of ViFM models for Traffic Anomaly Detection task:

Unlike the recent top-performing methods for TAD, which all have complex, multi-module architectures, TUE followed a simple encoder-only paradigm with a Video Foundation Model (ViFM) as an encoder.

After seeing how much better these ViFM models are both in accuracy and throughput, and how important the type of pre-training is, TUE focused more on obtaining good representations from learning with minimal architectural constraints, rather than from specialized architecture (and adding more context data).

For future research though, exploring how TUEs Visual Encoder could also improve these more specialised architectures, with additional context data, even further in accuracy, would be an interesting option to explore; and thereby addressing extension of those architectures for various modalities and tasks, address explainability, and in a large number of tools to optimise and deploy such models. It is unlikely however, that there will also be an improvement in throughput with such architectures; simply because those architectures are more complex, they require more processing time. So, depending on its application (real-time collision detection vs. offline processing of scene understanding) a choice for simple vs. complex architecture might play a role.

7.2.2. UC2 – AI-extended Situation Awareness/Understanding

[VIF] UC2.2 Developing the model demonstrated the importance of a **structured data representation** — the LDM and rasterisation pipeline proved crucial for effectively capturing spatial-temporal context. Integrating **physics-based constraints** within the AI architecture significantly improved prediction stability and realism. Finally, combining **intrinsic and post-hoc explainability** highlighted the value of explainable design for model debugging and trust, even if current methods still reveal correlations rather than true causal reasoning.

7.2.3. UC3 - Trustworthy and Human understandable Decision-making

As shown in Figure 54 UC 3 primarily addresses the post-deployment phase in the AI lifecycle. The goal was to increase the robustness and trustworthiness of vehicle control while using AI methods. To this end, an architecture was implemented and deployed in the vehicle that allows

different approaches for tactical decision-making to be dynamically orchestrated. Furthermore, a DNN for tactical decision-making was developed and integrated. Finally, approaches were demonstrated that allow the competence of AI models to be evaluated at runtime, for example, and to respond accordingly (e.g., through dynamic orchestration of planning methods).

Various difficulties became apparent in the process. For example, defining label data, in other words, the desired behaviour, is not trivial, as it is, for example, subject to individual subjective fluctuations. Furthermore, our implementation uses a complex representation of the input data, which makes the preparation of the data for model inference very complex.

Nevertheless, the use of AI methods for decision-making in automated vehicles shows great potential, such as scalability, human-like behaviour, and continuous improvement, meaning that research should be pursued further to overcome the aforementioned challenges.

7.2.4. UC4 – AI-based Traffic management

From the perspective of developing AI solutions for automated vehicles, the methodology to assess the impact of the introduction of AVs into a (city) network comes later in the AI lifecycle. However, the methodology itself is still in an early stage of its development. We have learned that using simulations to assess the impact of AVs on traffic under varying conditions is a viable method. It covers a wide range of traffic conditions and potentially incidents/edge cases and can support different market penetration rates of AVs and different types of AVs as well.

Using the methodology, it is possible to, for example, assess how a fleet of 100 robo-taxis would impact a major city. There are, however, some challenges to come to valid and thus usable results. The primary fundamental challenge is to accurately parameterise the vehicle behaviour of such a robo-taxi so that the simulation behaviour mimics the real-world behaviour. For the lower-level behaviours, such as acceleration and following distance, this can be done easily if the values are known. This would require the provider of the robo-taxis to share that data, which could be difficult due to the proprietary nature of such information. In addition, there are higher levels of reasoning, e.g. how to cope with incidents and other special/uncommon circumstances, which can be harder to mirror in the simulation. Those would require further customisation of the vehicle models and likely custom scripting – as was done for the incident used in this study - to implement the required logic. Implementing this logic raises another challenge, which is to determine the behaviour for the non-AVs which provides the baseline. That behaviour needs to be identified using real-world observations, which can be challenging if the scenario is uncommon.

Finally, there are some pragmatic challenges, which can be overcome with enough time and resources, such as calibrating a large network and the required computational framework.

8. CONCLUSION

This deliverable is the third in WP5 and describes the final evaluation for the use cases of the Althena project. This report concentrates on evaluating the results of the individual partners (as a continuation of deliverable D5.2 [7]), as well as the results of the joint work within the use cases.

This document is structured according to the use cases. The evaluation of the use case 1 demonstrator confirmed that all predefined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were successfully achieved. The system demonstrated high pedestrian detection accuracy (99.09%), robust performance in dynamic urban scenarios, and effective integration of an explainable AI (XAI) interface that enhanced user understanding and trust. Additionally, transparency goals were met through explainable model layers and comprehensive documentation, while the perception pipeline maintained real-time performance exceeding sensor requirements. However, certain limitations remain, including high computational demands, interpretational limits of saliency maps, imperfect uncertainty calibration, and a small trade-off between performance and explainability.

Use Case 2.1 – Collision Prediction with Hybrid AI Data Fusion Models – advanced the reliability and interpretability of collision risk prediction (CRP) systems by leveraging modern Vision and Video Foundation Models (VFM/VLM). Traditional CRP methods are limited by narrow Operational Design Domains and a lack of diverse training data, particularly for rare or complex edge cases. To overcome this, two complementary approaches were developed. Vicomtech introduced an ontology-based scene understanding framework using Vision Language Models (VLMs), integrating visual perception with structured semantic knowledge. This method enables explainable, context-aware interpretation of traffic scenes and enhances the detection of out-of-distribution events. TUE focused on Traffic Anomaly Detection (TAD) using simple encoder-only Video Vision Transformers (ViTs). Through extensive pre-training, including self-supervised Masked Video Modelling (MVM) and Domain-Adaptive Pre-Training (DAPT), these models achieved state-of-the-art performance with greater efficiency and robustness. Together, these approaches demonstrate that foundation models can significantly improve both the transparency and robustness of collision prediction systems. While current limitations include the need for better quantitative evaluation metrics, multimodal integration, and real-time processing capabilities, the results mark a substantial step toward safer, more explainable AI for automated driving.

Use case 2.2 demonstrated a comprehensive approach to enhancing situational awareness for automated driving in complex urban environments. Within the Althena consortium, multiple partners contributed to an integrated perception-to-prediction pipeline, supported by a deterministic, time-triggered runtime environment. TTTech Auto developed a time-triggered scheduling framework ensuring predictable timing and reproducible execution of containerised AI components. Siemens generated high-quality multimodal datasets and established a hybrid X-in-the-Loop testing framework enabling realistic system validation. Infineon implemented situational awareness features using YOLO-based models for traffic light, signal light, and object orientation detection, achieving robust real-time performance. Continental developed a modular AI perception system combining camera and LiDAR fusion for object, lane, and freespace detection, integrated into ROS2/Docker for seamless deployment. Virtual Vehicle focused on motion intention prediction, validating accuracy, feasibility, and transparency through KPI-based assessment. Across all modules, the demonstrator achieved reliable real-time operation and strong performance against defined KPIs, while highlighting key limitations. These include challenges in scaling computational loads, reduced robustness in highly interactive or low-visibility conditions, and inherent trade-offs between model performance and explainability.

Nevertheless, the results confirm the feasibility of integrating independently developed AI components within a deterministic runtime framework, providing a solid foundation for future development toward safe and explainable autonomous driving in urban traffic scenarios.

The use case 3 Demonstrator focused on Explainable and Robust Decision Making, combining machine learning-based tactical planning with rule-based software guardrails to ensure safe and trustworthy automated vehicle guidance. A Hybrid AI architecture was developed and deployed both in simulation and in a real vehicle, allowing dynamic orchestration of different decision-making modules based on their situational competence. TNO contributed methods for evaluating model trustworthiness through a competence metric, which assesses how well an AI system can handle specific driving scenes based on training data coverage and scene complexity. Results showed a weak but statistically significant correlation between competence and trajectory prediction accuracy, confirming that higher competence generally leads to more reliable performance. ika implemented and tested the Hybrid AI approach in real-world driving scenarios, demonstrating predictive planning with V2X data and robustness to unknown contexts. The system successfully explained its non-intuitive actions to occupants and dynamically switched between AI models and traditional planners. Overall, the work demonstrated that integrating explainable AI methods, competence assessment, and hybrid architectures can improve both the robustness and transparency of automated driving systems. Future efforts should focus on improving data representation, expanding contextual modelling, and enhancing training data diversity to further strengthen reliability and trustworthiness.

Use Case 4 of the Althena project investigates how AI-based automated vehicles affect overall traffic network performance, focusing on traffic management and vehicle-infrastructure interaction. Using a microsimulation of an urban network in Heemstede, various scenarios were tested, combining different levels of AV penetration, driving behaviours (cautious, normal, aggressive), traffic conditions (LOS A and C), and levels of AV trust in traffic management (TM) information. The results show that AV impacts on efficiency, emissions, and safety depend strongly on these parameters. Under normal conditions, cautious AVs tend to increase delays and emissions, while aggressive AVs perform more efficiently. During incidents, trust in TM information significantly improves traffic flow and reduces emissions in light traffic but has diminishing or even adverse effects under heavy congestion. Safety outcomes are complex, with cautious AVs not necessarily being safer. Overall, the study highlights that AV performance and network effects are highly sensitive to behavioural calibration, penetration rates, and traffic context. Trust-based coordination can improve efficiency in moderate traffic but loses effectiveness in oversaturated conditions.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] A. Forrai, K. Unni, V. Neelgundmath, H. Hotait, H. Abdolhay and I. Barosan, Safety assurance of AI-enabled sensing and perception subsystem used in autonomous vehicles, Springer, 2026 (to be published).
- [2] K. Lasinger, R. Ranftl, K. Schindler and V. Koltun, *Towards Robust Monocular Depth Estimation: Mixing Datasets for Zero-Shot Cross-Dataset Transfer*, 2019.
- [3] S. F. Bhat, R. Birkel, D. Wofk, P. Wonka and M. Müller, *Zoedepth: Zero-shot transfer by combining relative and metric depth*, 2023.
- [4] L. Yang, B. Kang, Z. Huang, X. Xu, J. Feng and H. Zhao, “Depth Anything: Unleashing the Power of Large-Scale Unlabeled Data,” *CVPR*, 2024.
- [5] H. Hotait and A. Forrai, “An overview of monocular depth estimation with applicability in intelligent transportation,” in *IEEE International Symposium on Computational Intelligence and Informatics (CINTI)*, Budapest, Hungary, 2025.
- [6] J. d. Ouden, “Athena D3.2 - Report on initial AI algorithm development,” 2024.
- [7] B. Hillbrand, “Athena D5.2 - Report on initial use case evaluation,” 2024.
- [8] T. Choudhary and e. al, “Talk2BEV: Language-enhanced Bird’s-eye View Maps for Autonomous Driving,” in *2024 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, Yokohama, Japan, 2024.
- [9] B. Hillbrand, “Athena D5.1 - Testing and evaluation methodology for AI-driven CCAM systems,” <https://aithena.eu/library/>, 2024.
- [10] R. Girgis, F. Golemo, F. Codevilla, M. Weiss, J. D’Souza, S. E. Kahou, F. Heide and C. Pal, “Latent variable sequential set transformers for joint multi-agent motion prediction,” *The Tenth International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2022.
- [11] H. Caesar, J. Kabzan, K. Tan, W. Fong, E. Wolff, A. Lang, L. Fletcher, O. Beijbom and S. Omari, “NuPlan: A closed-loop ML-based planning benchmark for autonomous vehicles,” 2022.
- [12] J. d. Ouden, “Athena D3.3 - Report on final AI algorithm development,” 2025.
- [13] M. Bansal, A. Krizhevsky and A. Ogale, “ChauffeurNet: Learning to Drive by Imitating the Best and Synthesizing the Worst,” in *Robotics: Science and Systems*, Freiburg im Breisgau, 2019.
- [14] K. Renz, K. Chitta, O.-B. Mercea, A. S. Koepke, Z. Akata and A. Geiger, “PlanT: Explainable Planning Transformers via Object-Level Representations,” in *Proceedings of The 6th Conference on Robot Learning*, PMLR, Auckland, 2023.
- [15] S. Pini, C. S. Perone, A. Ahuja, A. S. R. Ferreira, M. Niendorf and S. Zagoruyko, “Safe Real-World Autonomous Driving by Learning to Predict and Plan with a Mixture of Experts,” in *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, London, 2023.
- [16] D. Dauner, M. Hallgarten, A. Geiger and K. Chitta, “Parting with Misconceptions about Learning-based Vehicle Motion Planning,” in *Proceedings of The 7th Conference on Robot Learning*, PMLR, Auckland, 2023.

- [17] M.-K. Bouzidi, D. Bojan, D. Goehring and J. Reichardt, “Motion planning under uncertainty: Integrating learning-based multi-modal predictors into branch model predictive control,” in *IEEE 27th International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC)*, Edmonto, 2024.